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Prospective Diagnosis: Social-Ecological Inequalities in Green Infrastructures, Housing and Mobility in Brussels-Capital Region

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Submission date	November 2024
Dissemination level	Public
Keywords	Just transition; Social-ecological inequalities; Social-ecological systems; Urban studies; Futures studies; Prospective research

Summary

This report introduces the main results from the first phase of the [COGITO project](#), a prospective research project that explores scenarios for a just transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in the Brussels Capital region (BCR) at horizon 2050. More specifically, it presents the prospective diagnosis of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR in the three interlinked domains considered as part of COGITO: green infrastructure, housing and mobility. The main objective of such diagnosis is to *“understand, in a systemic and dynamic way, the present and past evolutions both of the system itself and of its environment”*¹.

This work is based on an original social-ecological justice framework that combines perspectives of the (social-)environmental and the ecological justice models. It considers five types of social-ecological inequalities in relation with intergenerational, intragenerational and interspecies justice: 1) the unequal contribution to environmental degradation, 2) the unequal distribution of environmental goods and burdens, 3) the unequal impacts of environmental policies, 4) the unequal participation in environmental policy- and decision-making processes, and 5) the unequal recognition of the needs of vulnerable/vulnerabilized groups.

The prospective diagnosis has involved the development of a retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR based on documentary research, exploratory interviews, and thematic workshops. In this context, the past evolution and current state of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructure, housing and mobility in the region, as well as the factors that have influenced these inequalities has been explored. This analysis has highlighted the complex and multidimensional nature of social-ecological inequalities in these different domains, alongside their many interrelated influencing factors.

From this retrospective analysis, the multiple factors influencing social-ecological inequalities in the BCR in green infrastructure, housing and mobility were identified and grouped into a set of variables corresponding to homogeneous themes. This has resulted in a list of 22 variables that has been jointly defined by the research team. To better understand the positioning of each of these variables in the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR and their interactions, a visual representation of this system has also been developed by combining two complementary tools: the prospective radar and the causal loop diagram. Finally, a retrospective analysis of each of the variables influencing social-ecological inequalities was carried out based on documentary research supplemented by experts' interviews.

All this will serve as a knowledge base for the second phase of the prospective exercise, i.e.: the construction and analysis of just transition scenarios to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in the BCR at horizon 2050.

¹ Goux-Baudiment 2013, p. 16, personal translation

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1. Introduction

Largely caused by the most privileged, climate change is destroying the living conditions of the most disadvantaged communities first and foremost. This is why we can speak of a climate debt. Global climate change and the resulting environmental degradation is also one of our greatest debts to future societies. A just transition is essential, because it will make it possible to limit the effects of climate change and reduce environmental damage while combating social inequalities. On the contrary, without a just transition, these inequalities should worsen under the pressure of climate change. Climate debt is therefore closely linked to questions of social-ecological justice. The environmental damage caused by climate change is unevenly distributed at different levels, both globally and within cities. To ensure just urban transitions to carbon neutrality and climate resilience, cities and regions must therefore focus on the "justice-sustainability transition nexus" and thus pay off their climate debt.

Against that background, this report presents the prospective diagnosis of social-ecological inequalities in Brussels-Capital Region (BCR) developed as part of the [COGITO project](#), a prospective research project aimed at building and analysing scenarios for a just transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in the Brussels-Capital Region by 2050. The development of the prospective diagnosis is the first phase of the prospective research (see Figure 1). The main objective of this diagnosis is to "understand, in a systemic and dynamic way, the present and past evolutions both of the system itself and of its environment" (Goux-Baudiment 2013, p. 16). It provides the knowledge base for the second phase of the prospective exercise, i.e.: the construction and analysis of the scenarios.

Figure 1 Overview of the Prospective Approach

The rest of this report is divided in five sections. The next one (Section 2) establishes the importance of social-ecological justice principles to work on a just urban transitions and presents the social-ecological inequalities framework on which this analysis is based. Section 3 introduces the methodology we implemented for developing the prospective diagnosis of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR. Section 4 explores the past evolution and current state of the social-ecological inequalities in the BCR and their influencing factors in the three domains considered as part of the COGITO project: green infrastructures, housing and mobility. Based on this retrospective analysis, Section 5 develops the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR by providing a definition of each of its influencing variables and a visual representation of this systems. The last section (Section 6) concludes the report.

2. The Social-Ecological Inequalities Framework

The COGITO project adopts a broad conception of ‘just transition’, which we understand as a social-ecological project aimed at addressing both social-environmental and ecological injustices (Laurent, 2023; Fransolet et Vanhille, 2023). In other words, this conception of just transition rests on **social-ecological justice principles**. In this section, we provide a brief introduction to the social-ecological justice framework, from its origins to current understandings.

The social-ecological justice framework combines perspectives of the (social-)environmental and ecological justice movements. **Environmental justice** has many definitions (Walker, 2012), though one that is commonly employed comes from the United States Environmental Protection Agency. The agency defines environmental justice as “the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, colour, national origin, or income, with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies” (EPA, 2016). The environmental justice movement has roots in the Civil Rights movement of the United States, and early environmental justice claims brought attention to the “environmental racism” facing people of color in the U.S. In its advent, the movement primarily focused on the relationship between poverty and race in relation to the spatial distribution of polluting industrial and waste sites (Schlosberg, 2007; Walker, 2012), or so-called “brown environmental justice”. The term has since broadened to include other types of injustices (e.g. the uneven distribution and provision of green infrastructure, or so-called “green environmental justice”) (Laigle, 2018; Jenkins, 2018; Schlosberg, 2007) and has spread around the globe, with governments at all scales adopting the frame of environmental justice in policy and plans (Walker, 2012).

Environmental justice is typically conceived of as encompassing three dimensions: distributive justice, procedural justice, and justice as recognition (Schlosberg, 2007; Walker, 2012). Gordon Walker (2012, pg. 10) defines these as follows:

- **Distributive justice** – justice is conceived in terms of distribution or sharing out of goods (resources and amenities) and bads (harms and risks).
- **Procedural justice** – justice is conceived in terms of the ways in which decisions are made, who is involved and has influence.
- **Justice as recognition** – justice is conceived in terms of who is given respect and who is and isn’t valued.

More recently, a fourth dimension has been included by many scholars: **capabilities justice**. This includes the range of basic needs and capabilities that humans need to function (Nussbaum, 2011). To be denied of all one needs to function is, according to Nussbaum, a matter of individual human dignity (Nussbaum, 2011). Some central capabilities include the ability to have good (reproductive) health, to be able to move freely and safely, access to basic education to enable imagination, thought, and reason, the opportunity to interact and live and engage with others (including other species), the opportunity to play, and some degree of control over one’s environment, in both a political and material sense. The capabilities approach often encompasses some of the same reflections and considerations of “justice as recognition”, as Nussbaum argues that the denial of opportunities (and therefore the ability to obtain all one needs to function) greatly overlaps with, e.g., gender, physical ability, age, etc. (Nussbaum, 2011).

While environmental justice has gained significant attention, ecological justice remains on the fringes, not yet integrated into policy or extensively studied. Previous conceptualizations of justice have been grounded in notions of “human exceptionalism and separation from the rest of the natural world” (Schlosberg, 2014, pg. 75). However, modern crises, including climate change and the biodiversity loss, make evident the inseparable nature of the human and non-human domains of the living world, demonstrating that the ignorance of human and non-human connectedness is “unsustainable

(Schlosberg, 2014). Recognizing the interlinkage between human and non-human life, the concept of **ecological justice**, or “doing justice to nature” (Schlosberg, 2007), brings the rights and needs of non-humans to the fore.

Bridging environmental and ecological justice, the **social-ecological justice** framework “emphasizes the interlinkages and interactions between social and ecological developments” (Grossmann et al., 2021, pg. 1410). As Schlosberg (2007) states, until now, environmental justice has typically excluded the needs of non-humans, while ecological justice considerations have not been thoroughly integrated with the needs of humans. However, combining social and environmental imperatives can help to ensure that humans are protected from environmental harms, while nature is protected from negative human interventions (Yaka, 2019). Given the specific configurations of humans and non-humans in cities, as well as the unique challenges that cities face, there is a need to study the application of the social-ecological justice concept in cities, a perspective that is all but missing from the literature.

Although many definitions of ecological justice focus only on the distributive dimensions of justice for non-humans, Schlosberg (2007) states that “once we begin to extend the community of justice beyond humans, even when we are exploring loopholes in existing distributional theories, we are stepping beyond distribution into the realms of recognition, procedural justice, and capability theory” (pg. 126). He claims, as have other before him, that we cannot consider the distributive injustices facing humans and non-humans without also examining the institutional and cultural limits to achieving distributive justice. For instance, an examination of the misrecognition of human and non-human needs is critical for explaining the maldistribution of environmental goods and harms. As such, Schlosberg advocates for bringing understandings of recognition and capabilities into the theory of ecological justice.

In response to the need to look beyond distributive justice, recent attempts have been made to extend the four dimensions of (social-)environmental² justice (distributive, procedural, recognition, capabilities) to the social-ecological framework (Pineda-Pinto et al., 2021). These dimensions have been used to assess environmental injustice in many (urban) contexts, however, they have not been extensively applied to the context of social-ecological injustice (or, for that matter, to questions of ecological justice). Drawing from the definition of these four dimensions in environmental justice literature, Pineda-Pinto et al. (2021) put forward definitions of **social-ecological distributive, procedural, recognition, and capabilities justice**. Their definitions tend to place a slight focus on the “ecological” dimensions of social-ecological justice, emphasizing the needs and rights of nature in urban contexts. To ensure a more balanced social-ecological justice perspective, we omit or modify certain parts of these definitions so as not to tip the scale in favour of ecological justice. The authors define social-ecological **distributive injustice** as “... the unfair and inequitable distribution of human-caused environmental bads across **humans and nature**” (pg. 5). **Procedural justice** is defined as the “equitable, transparent, legitimate, and empowering collaborations in decision-making, planning processes, and actions”, which is seen as essential for incorporating the needs of non-humans in political processes and therefore emancipating these silenced voices. **Recognition justice** is the “acknowled[ment of] multiple social-ecological actors and networks (as multispecies that co-inhabit within and across ecosystems), their vulnerabilities, across different scales, and their status within power structures.” A misrecognition may arise when the diverse needs of social or ecological groups are missing or not accurately presented. The definition of **social-ecological capabilities** from Pineda-Pinto et al. (2021), again, seems to focus more on the ecological justice aspects of the social-ecological framework (“...the capacity of nature to flourish and exist”) does not address social capabilities. Yet, given the importance of social capabilities for living a fulfilling life, we combine definitions of human

² We refer to “social-environmental” justice to make the distinction between environmental justice (i.e. to humans) and ecological justice (i.e. to nature) clear. There is no difference between social-environmental justice and environmental justice.

capabilities from Schlosberg (2012) and Pineda-Pinto et al. (2021). We therefore define social-ecological capabilities as “the basic needs and capabilities that human beings require to function, and that nature requires to flourish and exist.”

In the COGITO project, we adopt the social-ecological justice model (summarized in Figure 2) to assess the existing inequalities toward both humans and non-humans in the domains of housing, mobility, and green infrastructure in the Brussels Capital Region. The social-ecological justice perspective is particularly useful in the just transition discourse, as just transition aims to insert social justice concerns within ecological discourse and practices (Gunnarsson-Östling et al., 2022) and to jointly address intertwined social and ecological challenges (Fransolet and Vanhille, 2023).

Figure 2 Social-ecological justice model (adapted from Fransolet and Laurent, forthcoming)

The five types of inequalities in the figure below (Figure 3) expand upon the four aforementioned dimensions of social-ecological injustice to consider not only the ways in which certain groups are excluded from processes or unequally exposed to environmental goods and burdens, but to also capture the unequal contribution of individuals to environmental degradation (Laurent, 2023a), as well as the unequal impact of environmental and climate adaptation and mitigation policies on different social and ecological groups (see, e.g., Anguelovski et al., 2016) and the unequal recognition of the needs of subaltern groups.

Figure 3 Typology of social-ecological inequalities

Finally, we also put forward that these inequalities (in access and exposure, in impact and contribution, and in participation and recognition) can be acted out across different and between spatial and temporal scales, i.e. between 1) individuals and social groups within the same generation (**intra-generational** justice), 2) individuals and social groups of different generations (**inter-generational** justice), and 3) humans and non-humans (**inter-species** justice). By considering intergenerational, intragenerational, and interspecies justice, we adopt the ‘3 Is of justice’ approach developed by Gupta et al. (2022) as part of the ‘safe and just Earth system boundaries’ framework (Rockström et al., 2023).

3. Methodology

The development of the prospective diagnosis includes 1) the definition of the prospective system and 2) the retrospective analysis of the system variables. This chapter provides an overview of the methodology developed to carry out these two main tasks. More detail on the methodology can be found in the [COGITO Methodological Note #1 “Development of the Prospective Diagnosis”](#) (Fransolet et al., 2023).

3.1. Definition of the Prospective System

The definition of the prospective system consists of identifying and representing the different dimensions of the phenomenon studied in the form of a system. Such a system includes the ‘internal variables’, which are the variables that characterize the phenomenon studied – i.e.: social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility in the BCR –, and the ‘external variables’, which are the variables that characterize the social, ecological, economic, political, technological (...) aspects of the environment that influence (or are likely to influence) the phenomenon under study (Godet, 2007).

In COGITO, the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR was defined iteratively through three workstreams:

1. Exploring social-ecological inequalities in the BCR and their influencing factors
2. Clustering of factors influencing social-ecological inequalities in the BCR into variables
3. Representing the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR

The rest of the section introduces the methodology implemented for these three workstreams. Although they are presented sequentially, it is important to bear in mind that the definition of the prospective system is an iterative process involving back and forth between the different workstreams.

3.1.1. Exploring Social-Ecological Inequalities in the BCR and their Influencing Factors

The definition of the system of social-ecological inequalities has involved exploring social-ecological inequalities in the BCR and their influencing factors. To do so, we conducted a retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in terms of green infrastructures, housing, and mobility in BCR. This retrospective analysis aimed at 1) defining the multiple dimensions of these social-ecological inequalities, 2) documenting their current state and past evolutions³, and 3) identifying, on this basis, the main factors that have or could influence them, whether directly or indirectly. The objective of the retrospective analysis was thus to characterise the ‘heart’ of the prospective system – i.e.: the social-ecological inequalities in BCR – and to identify its direct and indirect factors – i.e.: the elements influencing the state of these social-ecological inequalities –. In this retrospective analysis, the social-ecological inequalities in terms of green infrastructures, housing, and mobility in BCR have been apprehended as three distinct sub-systems of the system of social-ecological inequalities in BCR (see Figure 4).

³ We looked at past trends up to 1990, a period of +/- 30 years, which corresponds roughly to the distance between the present and the time horizon of the prospective research (i.e.: 2050).

Figure 4 The social-ecological inequalities in terms of green infrastructures, housing, and mobility as three sub-systems of the system of social-ecological inequalities

For exploring the social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility in BCR, and their direct and indirect factors, we developed a methodology articulating three complementary data collection methods: documentary research, exploratory interviews, and thematic workshops (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 Methodology developed for exploring the social-ecological inequalities in BCR in each of the three domains considered (i.e.: green infrastructures, housing and mobility) and their direct and indirect factors

The **documentary research** aimed at developing an initial understanding of the different facets of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing, and mobility in the BCR, their past evolution and current state, and the factors that led to the current situation. Based on the social-ecological inequalities framework presented above (See section 2), we collected and analysed data on social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing, and mobility in the BCR from different types of sources, including publications from Brussels and non-Brussels organisations (ex.: Brussels Environment, Institut Bruxellois de Statistique et d'Analyse (IBSA), Observatoire de la santé et du social de Bruxelles-Capitale, Fondation Roi Baudouin, Observatoire des loyers, Observatoire du vélo, Observatoire de la mobilité, Satbel), archives from Brussels organisation (ex.: BRAL, ARAU), as well as research reports (ex.: De Muynck et al., 2021 ; Cooreman et al., 2019), academic papers (ex.: Dessouroux et al., 2016; Hubert et al., 2013; Strale, 2019) and books (ex.: Corijn and Vloeberghs, 2009; Zimmer and de Keersmaecker, 2019).

The retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility in the BCR have been completed based on **exploratory interviews** with Brussels and non-Brussels experts from academia, civil society, and public institutions. These interviews have been conducted with an interview guide inspired by the 'retro-prospective' interview guide proposed by Durance (2023), which consisted of two parts (see Appendix 2). In the first part, referred to as the 'retrospective', respondents were asked to identify the main social-ecological inequalities in the domain under consideration (i.e.: green infrastructures, housing or mobility), their past evolutions and the factors that influenced these evolutions. In the second part, called 'prospective', respondents were asked to discuss the factors that could influence the future developments of the social-ecological inequalities and how these inequalities could evolve in the short and long term. The aim of this second part was to integrate into the prospective system the factors that could influence social-ecological inequalities in the future and to gain an initial insight into the uncertainties and controversies surrounding future developments of the system. The exploratory interviews have been conducted between Autumn 2023 and Spring 2024. In total, 19 persons have been consulted, among which 7 experts on social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, 6 experts on social-ecological inequalities in housing, and 6 experts on social-ecological inequalities in mobility.

Following the main round of interviews, we organized three **thematic workshops** to consolidate the retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility in BCR. These workshops brought together Brussels and non-Brussels experts from universities, civil society organisations (ex.: environmental NGOs, associations fighting poverty and inequalities, urban movements...), as well as administrations and other public organisations. They included specialists on social-ecological inequalities in the specific domain under consideration (i.e.: green infrastructures, housing or mobility), but also more 'generalist' experts on social-ecological inequalities. Each of the three workshops was based on the same participatory approach designed by IWEPS prospective researchers (Calay and Claisse, 2024), which we have adapted to the objectives of the COGITO project. This approach, involving self-facilitated working groups sessions followed by plenary discussions, was conducted in five steps⁴:

- Introduction: Tour-de-table + Presentation of the COGITO project, the social-ecological inequality framework, the prospective approach, and the objectives of the workshop
- Exercise 1: Identification of the main social-ecological inequalities in the domain considered (i.e.: green infrastructures, housing or mobility) in BCR
- Exercise 2: Identification of the key factors that have led to the current state of these inequalities
- Exercise 3: Identification of the principal actions to be implemented at different levels of government to address these inequalities while ensuring the transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in BCR in 2050
- Conclusion: Presentation of the next stages of the COGITO project

The first two exercises were intended to provide input for the retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities, while the last exercise – which initiated the prospective reflection – was intended to produce insights on possible future just transition policies that will serve as a basis for the scenario-building workshops scheduled for autumn 2024. Besides data collection, these thematic workshops – which were the first stakeholders' meetings organised as part COGITO – aimed for participants to meet each other, to discover the project and to familiarize themselves with the prospective approach. The three workshops were each held in Brussels over half a day in March 2024. The workshop on social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures was attended by 15 persons, the one on social-

⁴ The workshops instructions are provided in appendix (see appendix 2).

ecological inequalities in housing by 20 persons, and the one on social-ecological inequalities in mobility by 11 persons. The outcomes of each of the three workshops are presented in appendix (see appendices 3, 4 and 5).

3.1.2. Clustering of Factors Influencing Social-Ecological Inequalities in the BCR into Variables

The retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility in BCR (see section 3.1.1) led to the identification of many influencing factors, which we had to cluster into a manageable number of variables (see Figure 6). A prospective system is indeed generally made up of ≈ 15-25 variables, with a higher number of variables making the scenario construction phase difficult. The definition of such a system therefore involves striking a balance between reducing complexity and maintaining a sufficient level of granularity to enable in-depth analysis. With this in mind, we first clustered the factors into variables corresponding to homogeneous themes for each of the three sub-systems (i.e.: green infrastructures, housing and mobility). We then compared the groups of factors obtained for each sub-system to develop a common list of variables. This work of clustering factors into variables was carried out iteratively throughout the prospective diagnosis via brainstorming meetings between members of the research team.

Figure 6 Clustering of factors influencing social-ecological inequalities into variables

Clustering factors enabled us to draw up a list of 22 variables including variables influencing social-ecological inequalities in the three domains and other ones influencing social-ecological inequalities in just one domain.

3.1.3. Representing the System of Social-Ecological Inequalities in the BCR

The definition of the prospective system has also involved representing the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR. A visual representation of the system is indeed instrumental for understanding the positioning of each variable and their interactions (Calay and Claisse, 2024). With this in mind, we have combined two complementary tools: the **prospective radar** and the **causal loop diagram**. On the one hand, by classifying the variables in a system representation structured into three concentric layers – 1) the ‘heart’ of the system (i.e.: the social-ecological inequalities in the RBC), the context that influences it directly, and the global environment that influences it indirectly – the prospective radar

enabled us to grasp the position of each variable in the system. On the other hand, by connecting the different components of the system with arrows, the causal loop diagram helped us for apprehending the complex interactions between the system variables.

We have first represented in detail each sub-system (i.e.: the social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility), before developing a simplified representation of the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR combining these three sub-systems.

3.2. Retrospective Analysis of the System Variables

The second main task of the prospective diagnosis consists in carrying out a retrospective analysis of the system variables. With that aim in mind, we have developed, for each variable influencing social-ecological inequalities, a 'variable sheet'. These fiche include a definition of the variable (scope, indicators and key words), data on its past developments (past trends and main events over the last 30 years), its current state (including current controversies, main uncertainties, and actors concerned) and – when available and relevant – (elements that could influence) its possible future evolutions⁵ (Durance, 2023 ; Lamblin, 2017). By providing a knowledge base for each variable, the variable-sheets are intended to support the scenario-building process.

The variable-sheets has been developed mainly based on **documentary analysis**. We have carried out a collection and analysis of data from different types of sources, starting with spatial and statistical data on Brussels produced by Brussels and non-Brussels organisations (ex.: Institut Bruxellois de Statistique et d'Analyse (IBSA), Bureau federal du Plan, Institut royal météorologique de Belgique (IRM)). When relevant, the same data on Wallonia and Flanders have been included to enable comparison and situate the case of Brussels within the Belgian context. For the political variables, we reviewed policy documents, plans, and strategies adopted by Brussels municipalities, the BCR, the Belgian federal government, the European Union and the United Nations. These data have been completed and put into perspective with insights from various studies and research.

Where necessary, the documentary analysis was supplemented by **interviews** with experts. Four experts have thus been consulted between March and April 2024 with a view to completing the variable-sheets⁶.

⁵ The exploration of possible future evolutions for system variables will be deepened as part of the scenario-building phase.

⁶ The purpose of these interviews was to fill in any gaps in the data on the retrospective of the variable, but also to start incorporating prospective elements into the variable-sheets.

4. Social-Ecological Inequalities in Brussels-Capital Region

In the following sections, we provide an overview of the current state and (when available) past evolution of the main inequalities in green infrastructure, housing and mobility in the BCR, and identify, on this basis, their main influencing factors. This summary pulls from existing reports on the state of the inequalities in these three domains in the BCR from, e.g. Brussels Environment, IBSA, etc. It also brings together findings from additional reports, academic publications, and archival data.

4.1. Green Infrastructures

Much of this section come from Brussels Environment's webpage⁷ and the work of Anne Franklin from IBSA.

4.1.1. Unequal Distribution of Green Infrastructure

The distribution of green infrastructure in the BCR is unequal, with per-capita green cover and green space accessibility varying across the region. According to Figure 7 from Brussels Environment (2023), eight Brussels municipalities have less than 10m² of publicly accessible green spaces per inhabitant (Saint-Gilles, Etterbeek, Saint-Josse, Schaerbeek, Ixelles, Molenbeek, Koekelberg and Forest), although Woluwe-Saint-Lambert and Anderlecht, with 11 and 12m²/inhabitant respectively, are close to the 10m² threshold. Watermael-Boitsfort, Auderghem, Uccle and Woluwe-Saint-Pierre are outliers, due in large part to the presence of the Sonian Forest and have more than 25m² of public green spaces per inhabitant (Brussels Environment, 2023). In terms of overall vegetation coverage per inhabitant, all municipalities except Watermael-Boitsfort, Auderghem, Uccle, Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, and Bruxelles-Ville are below the regional average of 69m²/inhabitant. Again, the presence of the Sonian Forest strongly influences these figures.

⁷ See webpage "Groene ruimten en biodiversiteit: stand van zaken": "<https://leefmilieu.brussels/burgers/tools-en-data/het-milieu-stand-van-zaken/groene-ruimten-en-biodiversiteit-stand-van-zaken>

Figure 7 Vegetation cover and green space access per inhabitant, represented in square meters, for each of the Brussels municipalities. (Source: Brussels Environment, 2023)

As of 1998, the degree of greening in the pentagon was 10%, mainly made up of public parks. Outside of the centre, this increased to between 30 and 71% (Gryseels, 1998). Today, the average vegetation cover in the Pentagon is 13% (for 55,000 inhabitants). In the first crown, this number is 26% (for 592,000 inhabitants) and, in the second crown, excluding uninhabited areas (e.g. the Sonian Forest), this number is 52%, i.e. double that of the first crown and four times that of the Pentagon. If the uninhabited areas are included, the average vegetation cover is 60% (Brussels Environment, 2023). The unequal division of vegetation around the region is linked to the **urban form of the city**, i.e. lower in neighbourhoods where buildings are dense, and blocks are often enclosed by continuous buildings and in the post-industrial fabric along the canal. Vegetation is higher in less densely populated neighbourhoods with open or semi-open blocks (Figure 8). The green zones are concentrated in the south-east and the peripheral zones to the west of the canal, particularly around the Sonian Forest, in the Woluwe valley, in Neerpede, Ganshoren, Jette, Laeken and Neder-Over-Heembeek. The Sonian Forest, which alone covers 10% of the regional territory, is located in the south-east of the Region (Brussels Environment, 2023).

Figure 8 Amount of green per building block, as a percentage. The three "crowns" of Brussels are indicated in black (Source, Brussels Environment, 2023).

In terms of changes over time, all municipalities have seen an increase in impervious surface between 1955 and 2006 (See Figure 9 and Figure 10, from a report from Vanhuyse et al., 2006). While this is not a direct measure of loss of green (a reliable measure of which does not exist), it can give an indication of surface sealing.

	Proportion de surfaces imperméables (en %)				
	1955	1970	1985	1993	2006
Anderlecht	19	29	38	42	49
Auderghem	11	20	22	24	29
Berchem Ste Agathe	19	30	39	40	48
Bruxelles	31	37	44	47	52
Etterbeek	60	65	65	70	76
Evere	16	33	41	41	48
Forest	32	41	49	51	63
Ganshoren	20	35	42	40	48
Ixelles	49	57	59	64	72
Jette	26	33	40	39	47
Koekelberg	48	59	61	62	69
Molenbeek	39	46	52	57	63
Saint Gilles	66	66	66	75	85
Saint Josse	68	67	65	71	80
Schaerbeek	49	56	59	63	68
Uccle	19	26	27	23	32
Watermael-Boitsfort	9	12	13	11	16
Woluwe-St-Lambert	20	34	42	41	50
Woluwe-St-Pierre	19	30	32	28	38

* Communes dont le territoire ne s'inscrit pas entièrement dans la zone d'étude

Figure 9 Proportion of the surface per commune that is impermeable, as a percent, in 1955, 1970, 1985, 1993, and 2006 (Source: Vanhuyse et al., 2006)

Figure 10 Evolution of the percentage of impermeable surface per commune between 19955 and 2005 (Source: Vanhuyse et al., 2006).

This trend has continued between 2006 and 2022; almost all municipalities have seen an increase in impervious surface between 2006 and 2022, with the exception of Saint-Gilles, which has seen no change (Figure 11). In terms of change as a percentage, Berchem-Sainte-Agathe, Jette, Saint-Josse, and Woluwe-St-Lambert have seen increases in impervious surface of 12% in this time period. In terms of change as a proportion compared to impervious surface in 2006, Jette, Woluwe-Saint-Lambert, and Berchem-Saint-Agathe have seen the greatest proportional increase.

Figure 11 Changes in impervious surface between 2006 and 2022. (Source: Data from Brussels Environment & WEO, 2023, own visualization)

It is difficult to know with certainty the net change in vegetation cover due to differences in the vegetation measuring conventions between the early 2000s and the present. Yet Brussels Environment has made an estimate of the change: Between 2009 and 2020, 90 green spaces or public spaces with green elements (between 10 and 30% permeability) were created (e.g. from scratch or lightly intervened). This includes 26 new hectares of green and 3 ha of “light intervention. During this period, 38 parks and squares were created. Also in this period, 22 green spaces or vegetated public spaces lost vegetated area totalling an area of 7.9 ha. The “net increase” in the supply of accessible green spaces or vegetated public spaces (corresponding to “real creations”) was therefore around 18 ha. In this time, the Brussels population increased by ~150,00 inhabitants, meaning there was an increase of 1.2 m² per new inhabitant (Brussels Environment, 2023). Again, Brussels Environment states that this data is not easily comparable due differences in measurement approaches from aerial imagery/remote sensing and margins of error – and there appears to be disparities between this increase in green and the strong increase in impervious surface from other sources (Brussels Environment, 2023).

A visual comparison was made with the high-resolution vegetation mapping carried out in 2016 and 2020, which found nine areas where the loss of vegetated area was greater than 1 ha and two areas where the gain in vegetated area was greater than 1 ha in this period. Areas of over 1ha of loss are mostly located in the north of the region (e.g. Haeren and Neder-over-Heembeek). Most notable is the loss at the Keelbeek site where the Haeren prison is under construction, which amounts to a loss of nearly 12 ha of vegetation. In some cases, works have caused a loss in vegetation, but this is expected to reappear once works are completed, as is the case with the former NATO site (Brussels Environment, 2023).

Brussels Environment observes a loss of vegetation due to strong pressure from urbanization in the north-east and south-west of the Region. Where the most extensive area of vegetation loss is detected between 2003 and 2016 (the former NATO site) is also the site that has seen one of the greatest increases in vegetation cover between 2016 and 2020 (Brussels Environment, 2023).

4.1.2. Unequal Access to Public Green Spaces

In a recent 2024 report⁸, Anne Franklin from IBSA summarizes the changes in access to public green spaces between 1981 and 2023. She also characterizes the state of access to public green spaces in 2023, according to their size and geographic distribution. In her assessment, she includes green spaces larger than 500m² with more than 50% vegetation or water surface cover, which are permanently accessible public or private spaces (accessible to all), and equipped for public use (e.g. contain benches, paths, etc.). Certain spaces are excluded from the analysis based on this categorization (e.g. the Marais de Jette, which is categorized as a “path in a green setting” and not a green space).

According to this report, in 2023, Brussels has just over 3,100 ha of accessible greens spaces⁹. This amounts to around 19% of the surface area of the region¹⁰. Only 6% of the accessible green in the region is located in the Pentagon and first ring (i.e. the city centre), and 23% in the second ring. Per inhabitant, there is an offer of approximately 26m². Yet, give the drastic differences in population between different parts of the region, this is only 5m² in the Pentagon and 4m² in the inner suburbs. In the second ring, this rises to 41 m² per person (Figure 12). Franklin notes here that standards from European and international levels often cite 9 to 10 m² of public green space per inhabitant as a minimum – therefore, the offer in the city centre does not meet these standards.

Franklin also notes that most of the parks in Brussels are very small, while bigger parks tend to be more appreciated. In the Pentagon, for instance, there is only one large park (Parc de Bruxelles).

② CARACTÉRISTIQUES DE L'OFFRE EN ESPACES VERTS EN RÉGION BRUXELLOISE EN 2023, POUR L'ENSEMBLE DE LA RÉGION ET PAR COURONNE

	Pentagone	Première couronne	Seconde couronne	Région
Démographie (au 1^{er} janvier)				
Population (nb. d'habitants)	54 722	447 205	717 486	1 222 637
Superficie du territoire (ha)	448	2 812	12 984	16 242
Densité de population (hab./ha)	122,2	159,0	55,3	75,3
Espaces verts accessibles au public				
Superficie totale des espaces verts (ha)	26	171	2 934	3 131
Part du territoire dédié aux espaces verts (%)	6	6	23	19
Superficie d'espaces verts par habitant (m ² /hab.)	5	4	41	26
Nombre d'habitants par hectare d'espace vert (hab./ha)	2 118	2 608	245	390

Source : Bruxelles Environnement, Statbel (Direction générale Statistique – Statistics Belgium). Calculs IBSA.

Note : la population utilisée pour le calcul par couronne est plus faible que la population totale de la région. Seuls les habitants pouvant être rattachés à un secteur statistique ont été pris en compte.

Figure 12 Characteristics of the offer of green spaces in the Brussels Region in 2023, for the entirety of the region and per crown (Franklin, 2023)

Franklin (2024) also notes that the surface area of public green spaces has increased between 1981 and 2023 (Figure 13). This is based on a comparison from Mireille Deconinck from 1981. According to her work, in 1981, Brussels had ~2,500ha of public green space, which covered 16% of the territory (excluding the Sonian forest, this was ~900ha, or 6.2% of the surface of Brussels). Based on data today (which has been adjusted to compare to these 1981 figures), **around 400ha has been added to the BCR since 1981**. This increase is fairly evenly spread across the region, with slightly more growth in the west and south of the region. Since 1981, the largest areas have been preserved. There have been many smaller spaces (less than 1ha) added, as well as spaces that were previously private that have

⁸ https://ibsa.brussels/sites/default/files/publication/documents/Focus-63_FRv5_0.pdf

⁹ Again, note that the Sonian Forests makes up a large part of this count – approximately 1,600ha, or 51% of accessible green space.

¹⁰ Only 9% if the Sonian Forest is excluded.

been made accessible to the public, new types of green spaces (e.g. Parc Maximilien, Nos Pilifs Farm, Miyawaki Forest), semi-natural or agricultural lands that have been developed for public use, and large areas that have been transformed into large green spaces (e.g. Parc Roi Baudouin, Parc de la Ligne 28, Tour & Taxi, Parc de la Senne, Parc de la Porte de Ninove) (Franklin, 2024).

4) PART DU TERRITOIRE OCCUPÉ PAR LES ESPACES VERTS ACCESSIBLES AU PUBLIC EN RÉGION BRUXELLOISE EN 1981 ET EN 2023, PAR SECTEUR STATISTIQUE (HA)

Figure 13 Characteristics of the offer of green spaces in the Brussels Region in 2023, for the entirety of the region and per crown (Source: Franklin, 2023)

However, certain areas that were included in the 1981 inventory do not appear in 2023, including some sports complexes, squares (because they are not green enough), and small areas that have disappeared due to development.

Also, Franklin highlights that per capita supply has stagnated over time. In other words, despite the addition of greenery, the demographic growth of the region means that per capital supply has fallen from 25m² in 1981 to 24m² in 2023. This is particularly true in the Pentagon and inner suburbs, which have gained more than 2,500 inhabitants/km² in this time period. For instance, in Figure 14 below, we see that, in 1981, 6m² of publicly accessible green spaces were available per inhabitant in the Pentagon, but this has decreased to 5m² in 2023.

5 SURFACES D'ESPACES VERTS ACCESSIBLES AU PUBLIC PAR HABITANT PAR COURONNE EN RÉGION DE BRUXELLOISE, EN 1981 ET EN 2023 (M²/HABITANT)

	1981	2023	
		Données comparables à 1981	Données du bilan 2023
Pentagone	5	6	5
Première couronne	3	4	4
Seconde couronne	41	38	41
Région	25	24	26

Source : Deconinck (1982), Bruxelles Environnement, Statbel (Direction générale Statistique – Statistics Belgium). Calculs IBSA.

Note : pour un aperçu de la sélection des données comparables entre 1981 et 2023, voir encadré 2 ; pour un aperçu des données du bilan 2023, voir encadré 1.

Figure 14 Surface of publicly accessible green spaces per inhabitant in the BCR between 1981 and 2023 (Source: Franklin, 2024)

Finally, Franklin provides a projection for several PADs of the development of green space (Figure 15). This shows, based on projected increases in population and projected additional green space, that there is a downward trend in access to green spaces in these PAD zones.

6 SITUATION PROJETÉE DE L'OFFRE EN ESPACES VERTS ACCESSIBLES AU PUBLIC (M²/HABITANT) DANS LES PLANS D'AMÉNAGEMENT DIRECTEUR (PAD) EN COURS D'ÉLABORATION OU DE MISE EN ŒUVRE EN RÉGION DE BRUXELLOISE EN JANVIER 2024

PAD	Couronne	Situation existante (2023)			Situation projetée (estimation)				Tendance
		Habitants (nb)	Espaces verts accessibles (ha)	Offre par habitant (m ² /hab)	Nouveaux logements (m ²)	Nouveaux habitants (nb)	Nouveaux espaces verts accessibles (ha)	Offre totale future (m ² /hab.)	
Porte de Ninove	P/1	14	3	2 432	34 395	740	0	45	↘
Casernes	1	< 5	0	0	20 000 + 605 kots	1 040	0,2	2	↗
Heyvaert	1	5 986	0,6	1	45 000	970	2	4	↗
Maximilien	1	7 212	9	12	84 325	1 810	0,2	10	→
Gare de l'Ouest	1	72	0	0	45 000	970	3	29	↗
Mediapark	2	0	0,3	-	152 673	3 280	7,8	25	↗
Josaphat	2	13	0,8	635	126 540	2 720	11,8	46	↘
Hermann-Debroux	2	169	0,7	40	157 000	3 380	3,2	11	↘
Défense (hors cimetières)	2	268	0	0	150 000	3 230	15	43	↗

Source : Statbel (Direction générale Statistique – Statistics Belgium), Bruxelles Environnement, Perspective.brussels. Calculs IBSA.

Notes : (i) les couronnes sont définies comme : P = Pentagone, 1 = 1^{ère} couronne, 2 = 2^{ème} couronne ; (ii) la situation existante est calculée à partir des données de population 2022 au point d'adresse et des données du bilan 2023 des espaces verts accessibles au public ; (iii) les données de la situation projetée ont été fournies par Perspective.brussels en janvier 2024 ; (iv) seuls les nouveaux espaces verts accessibles au public ont été pris en compte dans la situation projetée. Les parties de ces espaces verts qui ne seront pas accessibles ont été déduites de la situation projetée (Biopark pour le PAD Josaphat, périmètre de protection pour le PAD Mediapark), tout comme les espaces verts existants qui seront réaménagés (Parc Maximilien et espaces verts de la Porte de Ninove) ; (v) les nouveaux habitants ont été estimés sur base de 100 m² par logement, de 1 logement pour 1 ménage et de 2,15 personnes par ménage, de 1 kot = 1 habitant, et les estimations ont été arrondies à la dizaine ; (vi) pour la tendance, la direction de la flèche indique si l'offre par habitant est en hausse, stable ou en baisse.

Figure 15 Projected situation of the offer of publicly accessible green spaces (m²/inhabitant) based on the ongoing or completed PAD (Source: Franklin, 2024)

According to Brussels Environment, at present, around 22% of Brussels residents do not have a green space nearby their home (i.e. 200m from a green space less than 1ha and more than 400m from a green space more than 1ha) (Brussels Environment 2023). 42% of Brussels inhabitants do not have a green space of more than 1ha within 400 meters of their home. Schaerbeek, Brussels-Ville, Ixelles, Molenbeek and Uccle are the municipalities with the highest number of inhabitants who lack access to public green spaces (Figure 16) (Brussels Environment, 2023). Figure 17 shows the zones in Brussels

with a shortage of green space, along with amount of people per neighborhood with a green space shortage. There is a clear hotspot of shortage in the city center, around the canal, Quartier Nord, the Matonge area and around the ULB/VUB campuses. The number of inhabitants experiencing a shortage in each commune is shown in Figure 18. The greatest number of inhabitants experience shortage are in Schaerbeek, Brussels Centre, and Ixelles.

Figure 16 Percent of the population in the BCR that lives in an environment with a shortage in access to green spaces, by commune, against population lacking access (Brussels Environment, 2023).

Figure 17 Zones with a shortage of access to public green spaces. Circles indicate the population per neighborhood (Brussels Environment, 2023).

Aantal inwoners dat in een gebied met een tekort aan groene ruimten woont per gemeente
(gegevens groene ruimten 2023 en bevolking 2021)

Figure 18 Number of inhabitants that live in an area with a shortage of green space, by commune (Brussels Environment, 2023).

According to workshop participants, access to green spaces can also vary based on age, gender, physical ability, and mobility options. An example comes from Noël et al. (2021), which found that gendered elements of green space use can lead to feelings of insecurity, particularly amongst women. This insecurity can result in the avoidance of particular green spaces, which changes pictures of individual accessibility to these spaces. As of now, these identity-based analyses have been missing from assessment. However, given their importance in influencing accessibility, these should be further studied in the BCR.

4.1.3. Unequal Quality of Green Spaces

There is not much up-to-date data on green space quality in Brussels. A 2001 survey found a fairly positive appreciation of green space on a regional level (34% very satisfied, compared to 25% dissatisfied). However, there was a strong centre-periphery gradient, with a contrast between the old, densely populated city and the rest of Brussels Region. Very negative perceptions were found in the city centre and inner suburbs, with the exception of the area around square Marie-Louise. On the contrary, there was a positive effect in the south around the commune of Forest. A lack of positive effect was seen from the Royal Domain, unsurprisingly, as this area is inaccessible to the public. Beyond the railway ring road in the west, a positive assessment was seen with the exception of several zones in Anderlecht (Figure 19). Positive assessment was found in the east, beyond the main ring road, again, with several exceptions, including Haren, the Reyers district, the part of Etterbeek farthest from Cinquantenaire, and south-west of Uccle. According to Deboosere et al. 2009, *“this geography of satisfaction with the supply of green spaces is therefore a fairly accurate reflection of the real inequalities in access.”* The authors of this quality report point out that it is in the first crown to the west that there are the most children, the fewest private gardens, and the most densely occupied dwellings, where green space is also the least appreciated. In the second crown to the west, the portion of the population with access to a private garden is lower, but satisfaction with green spaces is relatively high due to the presence of several medium-sized parks. However, neighborhoods with best private gardens are also those with best perceived public green spaces (Deboosere et al., 2009). While these findings can provide an indication of satisfaction with urban green spaces in the BCR, more up-to-date data is needed.

Carte 8: espaces verts, indice synthétique par secteur statistique - DGSIE, ESE 2001

Figure 19 Difference between the part of the region that is "well equipped" and "poorly equipped" (Source: ESE, 2001; IGEAT, 2009)

Green per capita indicators (e.g. Figure 13) reflect the recreational pressure exerted on a green space. Greater pressure can lead to degradation of these spaces (e.g. through the excessive trampling of lawns) or conflicts of use (Brussels Environment, 2023).

Several publications in academic journals in recent years have focused on the intersection of quality and access in Brussels. For instance, research from Stessens et al. (2017) and Phillips et al. (2022, 2023) all find that quality tends to be lower in the centre and on green spaces where pressure is higher. Work from Phillips et al. (2022) explored how this lower quality influenced use patterns of green spaces as well. This research finds that quality is linked to travel time, as those living in the centre travel farther to reach green spaces and visit them less often, particularly those who value nature experiences (Phillips et al., 2022).

Anne Franklin, in her 2024 report, noted that the quality of green spaces depends on their location. She uses, as a proxy for green space quality, the ecological quality based on a map from Brussels Environment. She finds that 73% of green spaces accessible to the public have high or very high biological value. If the Sonian Forest is excluded, this is only 42%. No green spaces in the Pentagon are of high or very high biological quality and, in the inner suburbs, this number is only 5%, and 77% in the outer suburbs. It is mainly the larger parks in the second ring that have the highest biological quality (e.g. no pocket parks have high biological quality).

Other factors that influence the quality of green spaces, which emerged from the workshops, include the instrumentalization of green spaces for the markets, unequal exposure to different types of pollution (air, noise, soil...) when in green spaces, and conflicts of use that may arise for a number of reasons.

4.1.4. Unequal Access to Private Green Spaces

As of 1997, private garden spaces represented 32% of the green surface of the BCR, amounting to almost 3000 ha (Brussels Environment, 2002; Franklin, 2021) (Figure 20).¹¹ This includes gardens or private estates, certain spaces associated with roads, railway embankments, housing complexes, campuses, etc. (Brussels Environment, 2010).

Figure 20 Division of green spaces in the Brussels Capital Region (Source: Brussels Environment, 2010)

It is estimated that two-thirds of Brussels inhabitants did not have access to a private garden in 1997 (Brussels Environment, 2002; Franklin, 2021). It is difficult to compare this value to values earlier reported (e.g. in 1981 and 1991) due to differences in the phrasing of the question. At this time private green spaces were almost absent from the city centre (Franklin, 2021). There are no more up-to-date figures about access to private green spaces. These figures from 1997 do show that houses in the Pentagon least often have access to a private garden, followed by the first crown, with a clear east-west difference (Figure 21).

In terms of the size of green spaces, 55% of all gardens were very small (i.e. < 50m²), while large gardens (>300m²) were only 7% of the total number of gardens (Franklin, 2021). Only 14% of houses had a garden larger than 50 square meters (Franklin, 2021). According to Franklin (2021) **“There is a clear link between the surface area of a garden and its distance from the city centre”** (pg. 5). This relationship can be visualized in Figure 22.

¹¹ There is no more recent estimate of this number and, as such, it is not possible to say whether this number has increased or decreased (Franklin, 2021).

Figure 21 Percentage of dwellings with access to a private garden in 2001 by neighborhood (Source: Franklin, 2021, based on data from Statbel, 2001 census)

Figure 22 Percentage of dwellings with access to a private garden by size of garden (Source: Franklin, 2021, based on data from Statbel, 2001 census)

Private green spaces are poorly integrated into the Brussels' green network. Further, collecting data on these private spaces is challenging because they are often not visible, as they're located within housing blocks (Franklin, 2021). However, given their potential to be ecological link zones (De Schutter et al., 2000), more research on these spaces is needed.

4.1.5. Lack of Participation in Green Space Planning and Management

There is limited information on the quality of participation in the creation of green spaces the Brussels Capital Region. Based on interviews and focus group outcomes, it seems that participation remains insufficient. Participation is often short and limited (e.g. a limited timeframe to respond, on paper or online, to proposed plan). The public typically has 60 days to respond to a planning proposal, but this

is a closed-off mechanism. Thorough participation processes are lacking in part because they can be time consuming.

An example was given by an interview participant: In the Plan d'Aménagement Directeur (PAD), there is almost no participation; participation is limited to an information period at the end during the public inquiry. This means that development plans under the PAD, such as the Friche Josaphat plan, lack true participatory processes. In the case of the Friche, which received much opposition from citizens, alternative proposals were not regarded with credibility; when a "Plan B" was proposed, it was not clear the extent to which this Plan B was actually considered. There was no discussion about why the Plan B is or is not feasible. There has also been a bypassing of formal planning instruments and processes for certain projects, e.g. on Friche Josaphat.

It was noted in interviews that there were instances where participatory processes were followed but then the result did not align with what people said they want. Outcomes of previous attempts at real participation (e.g. with Tour and Taxi, Cite Administrative de l'Etat, Gare de l'Ouest) have been completely bypassed in the end. Planning therefore remains very top-down in Brussels.

Some interviewees gave examples of plans that have been more participative, such as the creation of Porte de Ninove, Parc de la Rosée, and the Parvis de Saint Gilles. These were said by some to be successful instances of public preferences integrated into plans through thorough participatory processes.

Further, according to workshop participants, there are inequalities in terms of who participates in these participation moments. There are disparities in the way different groups are perceived by politicians. According to workshop participations, in Brussels, politicians see citizens as white middle classes. In other words, the diversity of experiences and backgrounds are not captured in participation processes.

4.1.6. Lack of Consideration for Non-Humans in Urban Planning

Anthropocentrism in urban planning has led to urban conditions that can make thriving challenging for non-human species. Much of the below section is based on an interview with an expert in urban ecology and biology. The interviewee referred to cities as "filters" of species, as many cannot survive in urban environments. This doesn't need to be the case, certainly not to its current extent. In urban environments, there are "urban exploiters" (those who do better in cities than their natural habitat, i.e. rats and pigeons), "urban adapters" (those who are able to find recourses in cities), but most species are "urban avoiders" (species that cannot find the set of necessary habitat resources to survive).

Urban ecosystems are driven by species components. While species-poor ecosystems can function, they are much more vulnerable to shocks. When resilience is very low, ecosystems may collapse. The ability of species to survive in cities is largely based on the habitat provided and the resources available. Species can be flexible and dynamic, and each has a certain mobility, meaning they can move, to differing degrees, between habitats within an urban context. However, green fragmentation in urban areas can make movement difficult.

Pollution also has a large impact on non-humans, as it does on humans. In fact, because they are smaller than we are, non-human species are typically more vulnerable to these pollutants. Air, noise, and light pollution can interfere with communication and (therefore) sexual reproduction. Air pollutants can confuse certain species, making it difficult for them to find essential resources. For instance, a moth flying at night in a city with a lot of exhaust fumes will be lost due to the many scents present. This also impacts pollination processes. Noise pollution, often created by cars, contributes to elevated stress levels. Even the low urban hum created by electric cars can interfere with the communication and navigation of certain species. Finally, the impacts of artificial lighting on non-human species have been long overlooked. Artificial light heavily impacts the day-night indications of

certain species, which hugely impacts health. Due to increased visibility, light can also make certain species more vulnerable to predation. These impacts mean that the presence of strong artificial lighting can sometimes dictate where in the city certain species will go. The presence of different types of pollutants may make it such that even when a resource is available for a particular species, it cannot be exploited. Because species can only adapt to these stressors to a certain degree, we see much less biodiversity in cities compared to natural areas.

The presence of invasive species in cities can equally act as stressors to native species. It is easy for invasive species to dominate in urban areas because urban areas are not very species rich. This creates competition for native species. An example might be a green space that quickly becomes dominated by one or two invasive plant species. In extreme cases, this can lead to ecosystem collapse. In the BCR, there are clear hotspots of invasive species in natural spaces (Figure 23).

Figure 23 Location of exotic animal species in the BCR (Brussels Environment, 2023)

Climate change presents a big risk to many urban species – and a great injustice is the fact that they have had no part in contributing to climate change. This can be resolved in part by a well-connected canopy cover, which results in the cooling of the (soil) surface. But we might also see a shift in the species present in, e.g., Brussels toward species that are better adapted to warmer climate conditions.

Urban environments can often be unsafe for non-human species. An example comes from the “Animals Under the Wheel” (“Dieren onder de wielen) project, which allows citizens to log instances of roadkill, including the location and species type. Figure 24 an example of roadkill incidents logged in Waarnemingen over a 5 year period (Natuurpunt,n.d.). There is a clear overlap between biodiverse green spaces, busy roads, and roadkill accidents.

Figure 24 Example of a "Dieren onder de wielen" map, showing roadkill incidents in the BCR over a 5 year period (2017 - 2022) (Source: warnemingen.com, Natuurpunt)

Creating a just environment for non-human species involves creating more and better resources. Connectivity is important for non-human species – having several small but well-connected patches can be just as beneficial as having one large space. A gradual increase in the quality and quantity of resources available to non-species through, e.g., urban rewilding, will result in a positive ecosystem response and an ecosystem that is more resilient to shock. Certain management styles, typically those that are more “hands-off” (e.g. leaving dead wood to decompose), can be more beneficial for ecosystem health. This management style is more often employed in the urban periphery and less often in more central, “manicured” parks. Zonation in parks can be a solution.

The species composition in a city can give insight into how “just” the environment is for non-human species. Looking at certain challenges from a human perspective alone means that impacts can be overlooked.

Finally, education and information campaigns are essential here as well. Urban inhabitants, despite the best intentions, can sometimes make choices that have negative ecological outcomes.

4.1.7. Unequal Biological Quality

Figure 25 presents the “biological value map” of the BCR from 2020, which maps the biological value of all city blocks in the region. A biological grade of A indicates a very high biological value, while a score of E indicates a limited biological value. Sites with high biological value make an important contribution to the protection of regional biodiversity, including fauna, flora, and natural habitats. 19% of the region is categorized as “high” or “very high” biological value (Figure 26). This is an increase from numbers reported in 1998 by Gryseels, which indicated that 15% of the region’s surface had a high biological quality.

This biodiversity map clearly overlaps with the spatial distribution of income inequality in the BCR. This corresponds to a phenomenon known as the “luxury effect”, where “higher socioeconomic status

correlates with higher biodiversity” (Leong et al., 2018). This is due to greater investment in green spaces in wealthy areas, in private and public lands.

Figure 25 Biological quality of green spaces in Brussels, categorized into 5 categories from higher (A) to lower (E). (Source: Brussels Environment, 2023)

Totale oppervlakte van de verschillende categorieën (scores) van de biologische waarderingskaart en aandeel van deze gebieden met actieve of passieve bescherming
Bron: Leefmilieu Brussel - gegevens 2018

Categorie CEB	Oppervlakte (km ²)	% gewestelijke oppervlakte	Beschermde oppervlakte (km ²)	% beschermde oppervlakte
A	23,4	14,4%	22,5	96,0%
B	7,0	4,3%	4,7	67,8%
C	33,9	20,9%	8,5	25,2%
D	42,4	26,1%	3,3	7,8%
E	28,9	17,8%	0,2	0,8%
Totaal	135,6	83,5%	39,3	29,0%

Figure 26 Total percentage of the surface area comprising each biological quality grade (Brussels Environment, 2023)

Figure 27 Map combining the traffic volume on major streets, the degree of openness of building blocks, and the biological value of each building block in the BCR (Brussels Environment, 2023).

The map presented in Figure 27 is based on 3 types of data: (1) The "permeability" to movement of each urban block, which measures the degree of openness of the block (depending on the number of buildings at the perimeter level and inside the block) in relation to the surrounding blocks, (2) the volume of road traffic on each road section (2016 data), and (3) the biological value of each building block. Fragmentation of green space is a problem across all of Brussels, even in the Sonian Forest, which is crossed by different types of transport infrastructure, including highways and railroads (Brussels Environment, 2023).

A thorough investigation of threats to biodiversity in the BCR was reported in 1998. The report concluded that several things have contributed to the degradation of public green spaces, and therefore threaten biodiversity. Degradation is highest in the city centre, which is related to the insufficient provision of urban green for the social context. However, pressure also poses a significant threat to larger green areas in the urban periphery, particularly forests. In 1998, Gryseels wrote that the degradation of these peripheral forest spaces was reaching "frightening levels taking on frightening forms." Gryseels attributes this degradation to factors such as high visitor pressure, especially on weekends, visitors not respecting basic rules of conduct (e.g. leaving paths, destroying flora and vegetation, treading on and picking plants, excessive picking of mushrooms, disturbance of fauna, noise, new forms of recreation such as mountain biking, and stray dogs disturbing fauna). Creation of new paths can lead to fragmentation of habitats, soil degradation, direct destruction of flora and fauna, and disturbance of rest. Also, due to social context, there is "organizing" and/or making nature more beautiful (e.g., by so-called ecological plantings, removal of "dangerous" aspects, e.g. dead trees, making accessible of a previously inaccessible area). "Natural" area may also be taken for the creation of vegetable gardens, which is an important social initiative, but often at the expense of semi-natural areas (Gryseels, 1998).

More recently, demographic growth in the BCR, as well as a lack of compensation with new green spaces to accommodate for this growth, has led to increased pressure on green spaces, which can lead to compaction of soil, damage to spring flora (as increased use occurs in spring), to animal

reproduction, especially ground-nesting birds), and fauna in ponds (due to dogs swimming) (Brussels Environment, 2023).

All these pressures on urban green spaces were compounded due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Dedicated, 2020).

The biological quality of the region is linked to the soil quality of the environment. In an analysis of the soil quality of 800 sites conducted around the region, it was discovered that 40% of soil is degraded due to pollution, compaction, capping, and erosion, loss of organic matter, micro-organisms, and nutrients. The Brussels Region assesses soil quality based on 18 criteria. For a soil to be labelled “poor”, it needs to score poorly in more than 9 parameters. If the European calculation method was used (i.e. soil would be classified as “poor” based on only one criterion), 98% of the capital's soil would be classified as "degraded". In the BCR, chemical pollution affects the largest number of soils, followed by compaction, and then sealing of contaminated materials. As such, soils in Brussels are not very resilient and are therefore less prepared to adapt to the impacts of climate change. Rehabilitation and reuse of contaminated sites is often prevented due to the high cost of clean-up or risk management. Between 2005 and 2022, 1,651 plots of land in the region (with a total landmass of 1,011 ha) were treated and made available for economic, residential, and recreational activities. This decontamination process cost €493.6 million, or approximately €49 per m² (Walker, 2024).

4.2. Housing

The transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in the BCR raises important social-ecological justice issues. To understand these issues, it is essential to consider the preexisting social inequalities in the housing sector in which they have their origins. As stated by von Platten et colleagues, *“it is important to acknowledge these initial inequalities, present in building stocks all around the globe and manifested as segregation; as differences in tenure; as differences in residential density; as differences in the condition of residences; and as differences in the energy performance of residences”* (von Platten et al. 2020, p.8). The authors indeed explain that such inequalities form the starting point of the low-carbon transition in the residential sectors and that they can result in distributive injustices, as will be illustrated later. The social inequalities in terms of housing were, moreover, mentioned a lot during the workshop with the stakeholders.

This is why, the following section first focuses on the preexisting social inequalities in housing in Brussels, thus providing an overview on the multidimensionality of the affordable and quality housing crisis before focusing on social-ecological inequalities. In the analysis of social-ecological inequalities in housing, we have chosen to focus on those that are most relevant when considering the transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience.

4.2.1. Unequal Access to Affordable Housing

Decent housing is a right enshrined in the Belgian Constitution (art. 23), which fosters or even conditions the effective exercise of other fundamental human rights, such as health and education (Demonty et al., 2021). However, many Brussels households do not have access to it, the acquisition and rental of private or public housing being difficult for an increasing number of households.

a) Access to Housing property

The poorest households access property less than the wealthiest. An analysis of the share of owners and tenants by income decile for Belgium shows that less than 50% of households in the first two income deciles are owners, whereas this rate exceeds 80% for the four highest deciles (Aeby, 2019) (see Figure 28).

Figure 28 Share of tenants and owners per income decile in Belgium in 2016 (Aeby 2019, p.45)

Although we don't have data on the share of owners and tenants by income decile for the Brussels region, studies show that tenants tend to be overrepresented in the poorest areas of the region. The following map (Figure 29) reveals that the share of tenants varies greatly from one municipality/statistic sector to another, and that this percentage is much higher in the poorest areas than the richest. While the percentage of tenants is estimated at 62%¹² for the entire Brussels region, this rate exceeds 70% in certain areas of the center of the Region and in the “first crown”, particularly in the “poor crescent”. Conversely, the tenant share is lower than the regional average in many areas of the “second crown”, where median incomes tend to be higher¹³ (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles, 2022).

Figure 29 Share of rented housing in the housing stock by statistical sector in the Brussels Region in 2011 (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022, p. 84)

In recent decades, access to home ownership in Brussels has become increasingly difficult, especially for less well-off households. This is linked to **real estate prices rising faster than household incomes**.

¹² The share of tenants is much higher in Brussels than in the other regions, this rate reaching 34% in Wallonia and 26% in Flanders.

¹³ IBSA, 2021

Indeed, as shown in the graph below (Figure 30), the ratio between the median prices of apartments for sale and the median household income in the Brussels Region has risen between 1975 and 2013. According to Dessouroux and colleagues (2016), this decoupling of the purchase prices of housing in relation to the income of households has been particularly marked since the end of the 1990s. The authors observe that « This recent increase is exceptional in terms of its scale and duration ». They further point the unequal impacts of these evolutions: « This development is certainly not representative for the entire population, but nevertheless implies that it is the households with the lowest incomes who are penalized the most given that real estate prices on the private market align with the “purchasing power of potential buyers with the highest solvency” » [Romainville, 2015 : 21]. » (Dessouroux et al. 2016, p.9).

Figure 30 Evolution of the ratio of median price of apartments for sale in relation to median income per declaration in Brussels Capital regions (base 1975 = 100) (Dessouroux et al. 2016, p.10)

Several factors can contribute to explain the relative increase in housing price compared to households' income: a growing tension between supply and demand on the housing market generated by an increase in the number of households greater than that of the housing stock ; a significant increase in mortgage borrowing capacity linked to a reduction in interest rates and an extension of loan terms; the growing presence in the housing market of buyers (often of foreign origin) with high purchasing power¹⁴; the transfer of some movable investments towards residential real estate associated with an increasingly uncertain retirement system, a reduction in the attractiveness of bank savings or the lack of profitable and safe investment options; the (often speculative) retention of building land; and rising construction costs (Dessouroux et al., 2016)

b) Access to Housing on Private Rental Market

The least fortunate households also only have access to an extremely limited part of Brussels' private rental market. According to the Rent Observatory (2018), if we consider that a household's rent cannot exceed 25% of its budget, households in the first four deciles have access to less than 5% of the rental

¹⁴ Note that these buyers compete with other households for the purchase of housing, but also for the rental of housing.

market. Households in deciles 5, 6 and 7 only have access to 6%, 14% and 29% of the rental market respectively (De Keersmaecker and Sonecom, 2018). For their part, households in decile 8 have theoretically access to 65% of the rental market, and that of decile 9 to 93%. The figure below (Figure 31) offers a more detailed view of the theoretical share of the Brussels rental market accessible by income decile in 2018.

DÉCILES DE REVENUS	Revenu mensuel maximum	Part théorique du marché locatif accessible	
		Si le loyer ne peut dépasser 25% du budget	Si le loyer ne peut dépasser 30% du budget
2	870 €	0 %	1 %
3	1145 €	1 %	3 %
4	1322 €	3 %	6 %
5	1589 €	6 %	13 %
6	1932 €	14 %	28 %
7	2387 €	29 %	47 %
8	3075 €	65 %	84 %
9	4473 €	92 %	96 %

Figure 31 Theoretical share of the Brussels rental market accessible by income decile in 2018 (De Keersmaecker and Sonecom, 2018)

Between 2004 and 2018, access to housing on the private market decreased for all Brussels households, except the most affluent. As shown in the figure below (Figure 32), the share of the Brussels rental market accessible by income decile decreased between 2004 and 2016, then increased between 2016 and 2018. However, in 2018, only the most affluent households regained their level of access to the rental market of 2004. For other households, access to the rental market deteriorated overall between 2004 and 2018. The decrease in the share of the accessible rental market is particularly significant for middle-class households (deciles 7 and 6), which respectively went from 61% to 29% and from 44% to 14% (De Keersmaecker and Sonecom, 2018). These figures echo the observations made by Dessouroux and colleagues: “Those from the middle classes also have an increasingly restricted choice of accessible housing. If these households are not, in the strict sense, poorly housed, they find it increasingly difficult to adapt housing to their needs as their family evolutions” (Dessouroux et al., 2016, p. 11).

DÉCILES DE REVENUS	Part théorique du marché locatif accessible à chaque décile de revenu si le loyer ne peut dépasser 25% du budget du ménage				
	2018	2016	2015	2010	2004
2	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %	1 %
3	1 %	0 %	1 %	1 %	4 %
4	3 %	1 %	1 %	2 %	10 %
5	6 %	2 %	4 %	5 %	21 %
6	14 %	8 %	9 %	12 %	44 %
7	29 %	21 %	25 %	28 %	61 %
8	65 %	41 %	52 %	57 %	79 %
9	92 %	71 %	83 %	87 %	93 %

Figure 32 Evolution of the theoretical share of the Brussels rental market accessible by income decile between 2004 and 2018 (Observatoire des loyers, 2018)

This reduction in the financial accessibility of the rental market can be attributed to the **increase in rents**, particularly those of small and cheap units sought by the poorest households. Between 2004 and 2020, the real median rent and the real average rent¹⁵ in Brussels increased by around 30% and 25% respectively, while the average surface area of housing decreased during this same period (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022). This general increase in rents, however, concerns small and cheap housing more, and therefore affects the poorest households more. An analysis of the rental market carried out by IWEPS (2018) reveals that, in Brussels, between 2006 and 2016, the rent of the cheapest housing (1st quartile) has increased more than that of other housing (Figure 33). It further shows that, in Belgium, during this same period, the rent of small dwellings increased, that of medium dwellings remained relatively stable, and that of large dwellings generally decreased (Figure 34). The authors conclude that “high rents and those of large dwellings increase more slowly (or even decrease) than the lowest rents and those of small dwellings. The increase therefore weighs more heavily on precarious groups who can only afford to rent (small) cheap accommodation.” (IWEPS 2018, p. 58).

¹⁵ These amounts do not consider the indexation linked to the health index which reflects the evolution of consumer prices and serves as a basis for the indexation of rents, salaries, pensions and social benefits.

Figure 33 Evolution of average rents and 1st quartile rents by region between 2006 and 2016 per Region (IWEPS 2018, p. 44)

Figure 34 Evolution of average rents by type of housing between 2006 and 2016 in Belgium (IWEPS 2018, p. 45)

Beyond the difficulties of accessing housing, the rise in rent prices has other significant repercussions on least well-off households, including deprivation, over-indebtedness, even evictions. Households, and more particularly the poorest, are led to devote an increasingly large part of their budget to their rent. According to De Keersmaecker (2014), households with incomes below 1,500€ devote on average 60% of their budget to housing, while households with incomes above 3,000€ devote on average 25% of their budget to housing. The increasingly heavy burden of rent on the budgets of the poorest households can come at the expense of other essential expenses (food, health, education, etc.) (Dessouroux et al., 2016). It also exposes some households to an increased risk of over-indebtedness likely to give rise to rent arrears which, if they accumulate, can lead to evictions. In 2018, in the Brussels Region, the number of annual eviction requests is estimated at 5,000 and the number of effective evictions at 500. Home evictions without alternative housing can lead to homelessness. The number

of homeless (in public spaces, emergency accommodation centers and crisis reception structures), unhoused (in reception centers or transit accommodation) and poorly housed (in unapproved accommodation structures, negotiated occupations or squats) people in the Brussels in 2020 are estimated by Bruss'help at more than 5,313 in 2020. The **loss of income** suffered by certain households as part of the Covid crisis and the increase in energy prices linked to the war in Ukraine risks increasing the problems of over-indebtedness and, consequently, the number of residential evictions and homeless people (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022).

c) Access to Social Housing

In Brussels, access to social housing is also particularly difficult due to lower supply than demand. On 31st December 2021, 51 615 households were on the waiting list for social housing (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022). The waiting time to get social housing is estimated to be more than 10 years and varies depending on the type of accommodation. It is higher for accommodation for large families (i.e.: between approximately 15 and 20 years for a 4-bedroom apartment) than for accommodation for a single person or a couple (i.e.: approximately 12 years for a studio or a one-bedroom apartment)¹⁶.

Since many years, the number of households on waiting list for a social housing has significantly increased (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022). The figure below illustrates the evolution of the number of social housing and that of the number of households on the waiting list between 2009 and 2021 in Brussels (Figure 35). It shows that the number of households applying for social housing has risen more sharply than the number of social housings, resulting in a widening gap between supply and demand.

Figure 35 Evolution of the number of social housing and of the number of households on the waiting list between 2009 and 2021 (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022, p. 89)

The increase in demand for social housing is associated with several factors, notably the **deterioration of the financial situation of Brussels residents** and the **increase in rents on the private market** (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022). This evolution is also fed by the **downward trend in the stock of modest (often dilapidated) private housing at affordable rent**, qualified as “de facto social housing”, which is generated, among other things, by **real estate redevelopment projects** in central neighborhoods undergoing gentrification (Dessouroux et al. 2016).

¹⁶ <https://logementbruxellois.be/candidat-locataire/>

4.2.2. Unequal Quality of Housing

The difficulties in accessing affordable housing in Brussels push some households to make concessions in terms of the comfort, size or localization of their accommodation. Indeed, as explained by Dessouroux and colleagues, “One of the main symptoms of the housing crisis is the marginalization of a growing proportion of the population, forced to opt for housing that does not correspond to their personal or family needs. This is often combined with poor housing conditions and insecure tenure.” (Dessouroux et al. 2016, p.20). As a result, a great share of Brussels population lives in housing that is inadequate, with low energy performance contributing to heating problems and/or overcrowded. As shown in the figure below (Figure 36), the share of the population living in inadequate housing (i.e.: with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames of floor), with heating problems or in a situation of overcrowding in Brussels is higher than Belgian average. These rates correspond respectively to 26%, 6% and 29% in Brussels versus 16%, 4% and 6% in Belgium.

Source : SPF Economie-Statistics Belgium, EU-SILC 2021.

Figure 36 Share of the population living in inadequate housing, with heating problems or in a situation of per region in 2021 (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022, p. 85)

Among the Brussels population living in poor quality housing, precarious people are overrepresented. The next figure (Figure 37) indeed reveals that the share of the population living in inadequate housing, with heating problems or in a situation of overcrowding in Brussels is higher among the population at risk of poverty than among the population above the at-risk-of-poverty threshold. These inequalities are particularly important in relation to the problems of overcrowding and heating, for which the rates correspond respectively to 47% and 10% for population at risk of poverty versus 23% and 4% for the population that are not at risk of poverty (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022). This echoes the observations of the Belgian Combat Poverty Service, which reports that people living in poverty often live in poor-quality housing. In this respect, it identifies three particularly vulnerable profiles: “**long-term homeowners who cannot afford to carry out essential renovation work** (low-income homeowners), **purchasers of cheap housing in poor condition** ('emergency buyers') and **tenants who have no access to home ownership** (social and private tenants)” (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale 2019, p. 29-30).

Source : SPF Economie-Statistics Belgium, EU-SILC 2021.

Figure 37 Share of the population living in inadequate housing, with heating problems or in a situation of overcrowding according to the risk of poverty in Brussels in 2021 (Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale, 2022, p. 86)

The rest of the section analyses these different housing quality issues in greater depth, exploring their past trends and influencing factors.

a) Inadequate Housing

In Brussels, the share of the population living in inadequate housing (i.e.: with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames of floor) increased between 2008 and 2022. As shown in the figure below (Figure 38), the percentage gradually increases from 23.1% in 2008 to 27.1% in 2022¹⁷. However, our research has not identified the factors behind these developments.

	2008	2010	2013	2015	2018	2019	2020	2022	2018//2008	2018//2013	2022//2019
Région de Bruxelles-Capitale	23.1	24.8	26.7	26.8	25.8	24.7	24.9	27.1	1.1	-0.7	3.1
Région flamande	14.9	16.8	14.9	14.3	14.3	13.4	12.3	10.2	-0.4	-0.8	-8.7
Région wallonne	22.5	21.4	21.0	22.5	21.6	20.1	18.7	17.4	-0.4	0.6	-4.7

//: Taux de croissance moyens

La marge d'incertitude de cet indicateur est indiquée dans le texte pour la dernière année. Rupture de série: 2019

Statbel (2022), Communication directe 08/07/2022; Eurostat (2022), European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC), ilc_mdho01, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat> (consulté le 18/07/2022).

Figure 38 Evolution of the share of the population living in inadequate housing by region

b) Housing with Low Energy Performance

The Brussels residential building stock includes a majority of old and therefore potentially energy inefficient houses. As illustrated in the graph below (Figure 39), the share of housing built before 1980, which corresponds to the year the first energy performance standards for buildings were adopted, is estimated to 90%. This figure is higher than that of Flanders and Wallonia, for which the share of houses built before 1980 is respectively estimated at 65% and 80% (Aeby, 2019).

¹⁷ https://indicators.be/fr/i/G11_IDW/

Figure 39 Age of housing per region in Belgium in 2016 (Aeby 2019, p.10)

Outdated buildings combined with a **low renovation rate (<0,25%)** mean that a significant proportion of the housing stock in Brussels is of poor energy quality. As illustrated in the following table (Figure 40), between 2011 and 2019, 41% of apartments and 71% of houses have been assigned an F or G energy certificate. Conversely, less than 10% of apartments and 2% of houses have obtained at least the C+ energy label (Albrecht et al., 2022).

Label énergétique	Appartements	Maisons d'habitation
A-, A, A+, A++	0,57 %	0,16 %
B-, B, B+	5,94 %	1,04 %
C-, C, C+	12,13 %	3,29 %
D-, D, D+	19,95 %	8,89 %
E-, E, E+	20,41 %	14,92 %
F	14,31 %	18,89 %
G	26,69 %	52,81 %

Source : Bruxelles Environnement (2021). Rapport technique Énergie. RAPPORT STATISTIQUE POUR 2020: Certification PEB Habitations Individuelles, 17/06/2021

Figure 40 Distribution of apartments and houses by energy class (2011-2020) (Albrecht et al., 2022, p. 7)

The less privileged households generally live in older houses than wealthier households. In Belgium, almost 90% of households in the first income decile live in houses built before 1980 (and thus before the implementation of energy performance standards for buildings), whereas this rate only reaches 65% for households in the last decile (Figure 41) (Aeby, 2019). Moreover, as will be discussed later, the poorest households have less capacity to improve the energy performance of their homes (see section 4.2.6). As a result, they tend to live in less energy-efficient homes, which make them vulnerable to energy poverty (see section 4.2.4).

Figure 41 Age of housing per income decile in Belgium in 2016 (Aeby 2019, p.40)

In comparison with the houses in the private market, the social houses tend to be particularly old and with low energy performance level. As shown in the figure below (Figure 42), the Belgian social housing stock was largely built during the decades following the World War II to cope with the increase in poverty. They are thus likely to be energy inefficient (Aeby, 2019). This hypothesis is confirmed by a study commissioned by the Platform to fight energy poverty of the Fondation Roi Baudouin, which estimates that 44% of social housing in Brussels can be considered ‘very energy-intensive’ (Mathieu, 2018). Note that this figure is based on data from the period 2011-2016 and that the situation has probably improved since then due to the housing renovation policies implemented by the BCR.

Figure 42 Number of tenants per age of housing and type of rent in 2016 (Aeby 2019, p.46)

c) Overcrowded Housing

Overcrowding is the most frequent housing problem in BCR and the one for which the share of the population affected (29%) exceeds the Belgian average (6%) the most (see Figure 36). This can be explained by a greater proportion of small housing in Brussels associated to its urban character (Brussels Health and Social Observatory, 2022).

The problem of housing overcrowding in Brussels primarily affects poor households with children. In 2021, nearly half of the Brussels population experiencing poverty live in housing considered too cramped given the size of their household. Families with children are mainly affected by this problem (Brussels Health and Social Observatory, 2022). Inequalities in terms of housing overcrowding were also highlighted via cartographic analyses (see Figure 43). Dessouroux and colleagues indeed show that “Spatially, by far the highest overoccupancy rates are found in the poor crescent, where incomes are on average low, families with children are common, and elderly people are under-represented” (Dessouroux et al. 2016, p. 15). Alongside over-occupancy of housing, Dessouroux and colleagues also highlight situations of under-occupancy. Such situations are more common among elderly people and adults beyond parental age who continue to live in housing suitable for a family even though their children are gone. Homeowners and higher-income households are more likely to find themselves in this situation because they have access to larger homes (Dessouroux et al. 2016).

Figure 43 Share of population occupying overcrowded housing (2001) (Dessouroux et al. 2016, p. 15)

A trend towards **housing densification** contributing to an increase in overoccupancy of housing, particularly among low-income populations, is observed. This trend is notably revealed by the **increase in the size of households** in Brussels (Vandresse et al., 2021) (see Figure 44)¹⁸. Dessouroux and colleagues explain that “it is among low-income populations that the trend towards housing densification is undoubtedly most pronounced. This was already the case around fifteen years ago. But it is very likely that this trend has become more pronounced. In fact, low-income households have experienced the strongest growth in recent years, even though the rate of creation of new social housing has remained very slow and almost all the housing on the free market built since the years 2000 are financially inaccessible to them” (Dessouroux et al. 2016, p. 14). Different mechanisms associated with the shortage of affordable housing contribute to housing densification : the late departure from parental housing of young people, the forced choice of certain households to settle or stay in housing that is too small, the financial need of some households to rent part of the home and the constrained modes of cohabitation (e.g.: shared rental, group housing, accommodation with a third party or squats) (Dessouroux et al., 2016).

¹⁸ Conversely, in Flanders and Wallonia, the average size of households tends to decrease (Vandresse et al., 2021).

Figure 44 Past evolution and projection of the number and size of households in Brussels between 1996 and 2070 (Vandresse et al., 2021, p. 32)

4.2.3. Unequal Quality of the Environment Surrounding Housing

In addition to inequalities in the quality of housing in its material configuration, there are inequalities in the quality of the environment surrounding housing, starting with unequal impact of environmental nuisances on home comfort. The 2018 health survey carried out by Sciensano reveals that more than one in two Brussels residents (53%) declare they are bothered by environmental nuisances at home. As indicated in the figure below (Figure 45), these nuisances concern, in order of importance, noise (associated with road and air traffic, neighbors, rail traffic and nearby businesses) (42,8%), air pollution (28,1%), vibrations caused by traffic or companies (20,2%) and bad smells (10,9%). These nuisances are characteristic of urban environments, which contribute to explaining that the share of the population affected is higher in Brussels than in other regions of the country. Socio-economic inequalities in terms of discomfort at home caused by environmental pollution are observed. In Belgium, the share of the population bothered by environmental nuisances at home is higher for tenants (40.4%) than for owners (31.6%) (Charafeddine et Drieskens, 2020).

Figure 45 Share of the Belgian population aged 15 and over who declare having been bothered, over the last 12 months, at home by environmental nuisances, by region and type of nuisance (Charafeddine et Drieskens 2020, p. 19)

Between 2008 and 2018, the share of the Brussels population bothered by environmental nuisances at home remained stable, except for odors, which decreased. The graph above (Figure 46) indicates that, during this period, the share of the Brussels population bothered by at least one environmental pollution went from 53,2% to 53% (Charafeddine et Drieskens, 2020).

Figure 46 Share of the Belgian population aged 15 and over who declare having been bothered, over the last 12 months, at home by environmental nuisances, by region and type of nuisance (Charafeddine et Drieskens 2020, p. 20)

Besides comfort at the house, environmental nuisances deteriorate the quality of the residential area, especially that of the poorest populations. Still according to the 2018 health survey carried out by Sciensano, 36% of Brussels residents say that environmental nuisances in their neighborhood pose a serious problem. These environmental nuisances concern, in order of importance, the speed and/or volume of traffic (23%), the accumulation of rubbish (20,9%), vandalism, graffiti or deliberate damage to property (16,4%), and the lack of access to parks or other public green or recreational spaces¹⁹ (6,6%) (see Figure 47). The share of the Brussels population living in a neighborhood where one or more of these environmental nuisances poses a serious problem is higher than in Wallonia (24,4%) and Flanders (20,8%), which can – again – be explained by the urban character of Brussels. Besides regional inequalities, the 2018 health survey also indicates socio-economic disparities in the perception of environmental nuisances in the neighborhood. In Brussels, people with a diploma not exceeding lower secondary education are significantly more likely than people with higher education qualifications to declare that nuisances in the neighborhood of residence pose a serious problem. Likewise, people living in social/free housing are more affected than owners (Charafeddine et Drieskens, 2020).

¹⁹ Inequalities in access to green spaces are analyzed in more detail in the section devoted to social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures (see section 4.1).

Figure 47 Share of the population aged 15 and over who declare that environmental nuisance poses a serious problem in the neighbourhood of residence, by region and type of nuisance in Belgium in 2018 (Charafeddine et Drieskens 2020, p. 15)

Between 2013 and 2018, the share of the population saying they are affected by the speed and/or volume of traffic, the accumulation of rubbish, vandalism, and the lack of access to green spaces has decreased. As shown in the figure below (Figure 48), the share of the Brussels population declaring themselves affected by one or more of these nuisances decreased by 10% during this period (Charafeddine et Drieskens, 2020).

Figure 48 Evolution of the share of the Belgian population aged 15 and over who declare that environmental nuisance poses a serious problem in the neighbourhood of residence, by region and type of nuisance between 2013 and 2018 (Charafeddine et Drieskens 2020, p. 15)

Finally, inequalities in the availability of local services and equipment are also observed. De Muynck et al (2021) argue that accessibility to leisure or sports infrastructure is higher in wealthier peripheral areas than in poorer central areas.

4.2.4. Unequal Access to Essential Energy Services in Housing

In BCR, important inequalities in access to essential energy services in housing are observed. Indeed, according to the 2021 Energy poverty Barometer of the Foundation Roi Beaudoin, 27,4% of Brussels

households were affected by at least one form of energy poverty²⁰. As shown in the graph below (Figure 49), this percentage is higher than Belgian average, which corresponds to 20,6%. Considering the different forms of energy poverty²¹, the share of Brussels households affected by measured energy poverty (PEm), hidden energy poverty (PEc) and perceived energy poverty (PEr) correspond respectively to 12.4%, 12.3% and 5.3%. While measured energy poverty (PEm) in Brussels is slightly lower than the Belgian average (14,9%), hidden energy poverty far exceeds the national average (4,5%) and that of Flanders (3,9%) and Wallonia (5%) (Meyer and Coene, 2023). The authors explain that this difference between Brussels and the other regions could come “from the essentially urban character of Brussels with an increased presence of small housing (apartments) and adjoining housing (apartments, row houses), but also from a stronger tendency to under-consume among urban households in energy poverty as explained by Ute Dubois in her analysis of fuel poverty situations in France” (Ibidem, p. 27). Perceived energy poverty (PEr) in Brussels is also higher than Belgian average (3,2%), but similar to that of Wallonia (5,4%).

Source : données BE-SILC 2019-2021 ; Statbel ; calculs propres

Figure 49 Share of household affected by at least one form of energy poverty in Belgium and per region between 2019 and 2021 (Meyer and Coene 2023, p. 25)

Households with lower income tend to be more affected by energy poverty. The following graph shows the share of Belgian households in PEm, PEc, PEr or total PE by decile of equivalent disposable income in 2021 (Figure 50). It reveals that the households of the three first decile have a greater propensity to be affected by one or more forms of energy poverty than the wealthiest ones. However, it seems important to emphasize that for each income decile, situations of energy poverty and non-energy

²⁰ Water poverty is also a major problem in the BCR (Meyer and Coene, 2022). However, this issue will not be addressed in this analysis, as we have chosen to focus on the inequalities that are most relevant when considering the transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience.

²¹ The Energy poverty Barometer of the Fondation Roi Beaudoin (Meyer and Coene, 2023) combines three main indicators of energy poverty, which aims at representing the multiple dimensions of energy poverty: measured energy poverty (PEm), hidden energy poverty (PEc) and perceived energy poverty (PEr). The measured energy poverty (PEm) focuses on the “households whose energy expenditure is considered “abnormally” high in relation to their disposable income after deduction of the cost of housing” (Meyer and Coene 2023, p. 25). Conversely, the hidden energy poverty (PEc) targets the “households whose energy expenditure is considered “abnormally” low compared to an equivalent household (number of people, number of rooms in the home), indicating a high risk of deprivation in relation to the basic needs of the household” (Ibidem, p.27). Finally, the perceived energy poverty (PEr) reflects the “experience and feelings of households in relation to their (financial) capacity to meet energy bills” (Ibidem, p.29).

poverty coexist. The PEm is the form of energy poverty, the evolution of which has the strongest correlation with income levels. This form of energy poverty indeed concerns respectively 57.8% and 37.5% of households in decile 1 and 2, compared to less than 1% of households in deciles 9 and 10. Besides households with low incomes, other (partly overlapping) social groups are also particularly vulnerable to energy poverty, including single households, single-parent families, women, seniors and tenants (especially social tenants) (Meyer and Coene, 2023).

Source : BE-SILC 2021 ; Statbel ; calculs propres

Figure 50 Share of households in PEm, PEc, PEr and total PE by decile of equivalent disposable income in 2021 (Meyer and Coene 2023, p. 33)

Low-income levels, poor energy quality of housing and high energy prices are often identified as the main factors causing energy poverty (Meyer and Maréchal, 2016; Pye and al., 2015). Low-income and poor energy quality of housing can be seen as intersecting factors, since, as explained previously, poorer households tend to live in housing with poorer energy insulation (see section 4.2.3). Other determinants of energy poverty have also been identified in the literature. Thus, as Meyer and Maréchal explain, "the **composition of the household, the age or state of health of its members, as well as the professional status of household members** will influence energy needs, either through increased presence in the dwelling, or through different physiological needs (for example, a person who is not very mobile will generally need a higher ambient temperature to achieve a pleasant level of comfort)" (Meyer and Maréchal 2016, p. 3).

If the causes of fuel poverty are many, so are its negative consequences. A household in a situation of fuel poverty will either have to restrict its energy consumption below its basic needs (e.g., by not heating its home sufficiently or avoiding running certain energy-consuming appliances) or forgo other expenses in order to access essential energy services, or face bill payment delays that can lead to energy cuts and/or indebtedness. This can generate considerable impacts on the health and well-being of people affected and exacerbate social exclusion. Energy restrictions and cuts can also contribute to a deterioration in housing quality. The consequences of energy poverty can reinforce some of the factors behind this situation and poverty in general (Meyer and Maréchal, 2016). In this sense, Meyer and Maréchal assert that "the risk of finding oneself trapped in a negative spiral is therefore very present, locking certain households into a more structural situation of (energy) poverty" (Meyer and Maréchal 2016, p. 3).

Between 2014 and 2023²², energy poverty has been relatively stable in Belgium. This stability is associated with a drop in the energy bill at constant price (in particular due to a **mild climate** and a **lower energy prices**) offset by a decrease in the disposable income of households after deduction of housing costs (related to a **stagnation of disposable income** combined with an **increase in the cost of housing**, in particular for tenants of small housing). More specifically for the 2020-2021 period, the **extension²³ of the granting of the energy social tariff** to beneficiaries of the increased intervention and the various **social measures** linked to the pandemic and the floods in Wallonia have contributed to stabilizing energy poverty in Belgium (Meyer and Coene, 2023). Although the data are not available yet, we can expect an increase in energy poverty in 2022 and 2023 linked to the surge in energy prices. Brussels Health and Social Observatory indeed points that “The increase in energy prices greatly amplifies this already existing problem, and places a significant burden on the budgets of the most precarious, but also of the middle classes” (Brussels Health and Social Observatory 2022, p. 90).

4.2.5. Unequal Energy Consumption and Associated GHG Emissions in Housing

Although they generally live in houses with low energy performance, the poorest households tend to consume less energy and therefore emit less GHG than wealthier households. Research exploring the association between the carbon footprint and the socio-economic characteristics of Belgian households (Lévy et al., 2021) reveals that the GHG emitted by Belgian households for housing increase with the **level of income**, as illustrated in the figure below (Figure 51). This research however suggests that the GHG emissions in housing are less influenced by income than other emission categories like transport and consumption of goods and services. The authors explain the low income elasticity of housing emissions by the fact that the energy consumption in housing is aimed at satisfying basic needs (e.g.: heating). The research further reveals that the main factor explaining differences in housing GHG emissions is the **characteristics – and more specifically the size – of the dwelling**, with lower emissions for households living in semi-detached houses or apartments compared with households living in detached houses. In this regard, the authors explain that “Detached houses tend to have higher heating requirements than other types of dwellings, with larger surfaces and lower energy performance than apartments” (Lévy et al. 2021, p. 4).

²² In 2023, the ninth edition of the Energy Poverty Barometer from the Roi Beaudoin Foundation was published.

²³ While the gas and electricity social tariff is seen as an important tool for preventing energy poverty, several actors, including the Belgian Combat Poverty Service, point to the need to broaden the group of entitled beneficiaries (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale, 2019). Indeed, access to the social tariff is linked to status criteria and not to income level, which means that for equivalent incomes, some households will have access to this aid while others will not.

Figure 51 GHG emission per capita by product type for each decile of equivalent income (Lévy et al. 2021)

4.2.6. Unequal Capacity to Decarbonize Housing

To ensure the transition to climate neutrality by 2050, the sector of residential buildings should be (almost) fully decarbonized. Reaching zero GHG emissions in housing requires profound and rapid changes supported by both technological, social and behavioral innovations. It is indeed necessary 1) to increase significantly the renovation rate and depth of the residential building stock; 2) to replace fossil fuels technologies by electric devices (heat pumps) and by pollution-free biomass and synthetic fuels (hydrogen, e-gases and e-liquids) technologies where electrification is technically or economically not feasible; 3) to decarbonize the electricity production, but also 4) to implement various behavioral and cultural changes in terms of space use (reduction of the living space per person and reduction of the percentage of this space which is heated), heating and cooling behaviors (reduction of the comfort temperature in winter, increase of the comfort temperature in summer and reduction of the consumption of hot water), and appliance use (FPS Health - DG Environment - Climate Change Service, 2021).

There are currently major inequalities in capacity to decarbonize housing, starting with unequal capacity to carry out home energy renovation and to acquire (smart) low-carbon energy devices (ex.: energy-efficient heating system, solar panels...). Poorer households who, as we saw earlier (see section 4.2.2), tend to live in housing of poor (energy) quality, generally have less capacity to improve their dwelling. Based on consultations with people living in poverty and their association, the Belgian Combat Poverty Service has indeed highlighted major difficulties faced by poor homeowners in acquiring low-carbon technologies for their home due to a **lack of financial resources**: “There are various ways of remedying this poor housing quality and energy performance, but they are not affordable for low-income population groups: insulation work, energy-efficient appliances, installation of photovoltaic panels or a heat pump, ... Many households - who own their own homes - do not have the necessary means for a complete renovation.” (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale 2019, p. 30). Albrecht and Hamels (2021) further show that nearly half of Flemish homeowners under the age of 65 do not have the financial means to renovate their homes to reach an energy performance level in line with 2050 climate targets (i.e.: PEB A label). Considering that the average household income in the BCR is +/- 25% lower than in Flanders, Manuelli and Meyer (2023) assert that the proportion of Brussels homeowners lacking the means to renovate their homes should be similar or even higher. Besides low-income homeowners, tenants also tend to lack the capacity to renovate their homes. In this respect, the Belgian Combat Poverty Service asserts that “the situation is even more difficult for tenants” due to the **'split incentive' effect** (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale 2019, p. 30). This well-documented obstacle to the renovation of rented buildings arises from the divergence of interest between landlords and tenants in investing in

energy-efficient renovation (Castellazzi et al., 2017). Meyer and Maréchal explain that "when it comes to energy renovation in the rental sector, [...] 'split incentive' is particularly present, since the investment burden falls on the property owner, whereas it is the occupant (the tenant) who will enjoy the main benefits of the operation, namely increased comfort and lower energy bills" (Meyer and Maréchal 2016, p. 4-5). The BCR strives to help poor homeowners and tenants renovate their homes via a system of subsidies, but, as we'll see later (see section 4.2.7), many targeted households don't benefit. Alongside low-income homeowners and tenants, condominium owners also have less capacity to renovate their homes. This can be explained by the **difficulties associated with renovation of common areas (ex.: roofs, shared boilers) involving multiple owners with different interests**.

In addition to inequalities in access to technological innovations to decarbonize housing, there are also inequalities in access to social and behavioral innovations. Indeed, while some consider energy citizenship initiatives as a means of enabling more households to adopt low-carbon alternatives in their homes, others point to inequalities in access to these initiatives. In this regard, the Belgian Combat Poverty Service observes that "In the meantime, initiatives such as grouped energy purchases, citizen energy cooperatives and collective solar panel projects are springing up in various sectors of society... For various reasons, people living in poverty have little access to them. For example, paying a share in an energy cooperative is problematic for a **low-income** person." (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale 2019, p. 32). Moreover, although little documented today, some also identify inequalities in the ability to reduce energy consumption associated with heating through 'slow heating' practices²⁴. The SlowHeat project has indeed revealed that slow heating practices cannot be implemented in an **unsanitary building with humidity problems**, as these problems could be exacerbated by a reduction in temperature. Yet, households in (energy) poverty, who tend to live in poor quality houses (see section 4.2.2), are more often faced with these types of problems, which reduces their ability to adopt slow heating practices. In addition, slow heating practices require certain initial **investments** which, although much lower than those necessary to renovate the home, may be difficult to achieve for poorer households (Sobczak, 2023).

4.2.7. Unequal Impact of Housing Decarbonization Policies

The poorest households contribute the least to GHG emissions of the residential sector (see section 4.2.5) but tend to bear the greatest burden of the policies aimed at decarbonizing this sector and to benefit little from their advantages (von Platten et al., 2020; Grossmann, 2019).

Policies and measures aimed at ensuring the transition to carbon neutrality in the residential sector by 2050 often focus on the refurbishment of buildings with low energy performances, buildings in which the poorest households are, as mentioned above, over-represented (von Platten et al., 2020). The energy renovation of the least energy-efficient housing is indeed one of the key axes of the European low-carbon transition policy, which requires Member States to integrate into their long-term renovation strategies "an overview of policies and actions to target the worst performing segments of the national building stock" (European Commission 2018, p.8). The energy renovation of the dwellings of the poorest households can improve their living conditions, reduce their energy bill and, consequently, contribute to fight energy poverty, which, as said before, concerns more than one in four Brussels households, among which the least well-off are over-represented (Meyer and Coene, 2023) (see section 4.2.4). However, research shows that energy refurbishment policies benefit low-income households very little and can negatively impact them.

In Brussels, the main instrument of the energy renovation policy of the housing stock is the **'Renolution' subsidies scheme**²⁵. This scheme is designed to help Brussels residents make investments

²⁴ Examples of 'slow heat' practices can be found here <https://www.slowheat.org/about-1>

²⁵ <https://renolution.brussels/fr/les-primas-renolution-2023>

to improve the quality of their buildings, so as to reduce energy consumption and make them more comfortable and attractive. Since the first energy subsidies were introduced in 2004, the Brussels region has reformed the scheme several times, in particular to promote access to these premiums among certain target groups. Since 2011, premiums have thus been calculated according to the applicant's income level, with higher premiums for those on lower incomes. Three categories are considered to calculate the amounts granted: 'Category III' for low income, 'Category II' for average income and 'Category I' for the other level of income. In addition, to encourage the renovation of rented accommodation which, as explained in the previous section (section 4.2.6), tends to be hampered by split incentive effects, the region has been granting access to the preferential category (Category III) to landlords since 2016. The 2016 reform also included condominiums in the preferential category to encourage renovation of this type of housing, which also prove to be difficult (see section 4.2.6).

According to the 2022 energy bonus evaluation carried out by Bruxelles Environnement (2023), the system of higher bonuses for low-income households, landlords and condominiums has encouraged these target groups to carry out energy renovation work. This evaluation indeed reveals that 60% of the total amount granted goes to the preferred category (Category III). Regarding the distribution of premiums granted to households according to income category, it shows that low-income households (Category III) have benefited from more premiums than others, and for a much higher amount (see Figure 52). It also points out that the increase in average premiums between 2020 and 2022 is greater for low-income households than other income categories. Concerning the other target groups, the evaluation shows that between 2020 and 2022, the number of premiums for landlords and condominium has increased in terms of both the number and the amount of premiums (Bruxelles Environnement, 2023).

Catégorie de revenus	de	Nombre de primes octroyées	Montant total octroyé	Montant moyen 2022	Montant moyen 2021	Montant moyen 2020
Catégorie I - base		4.106	€ 4.493.939	€ 1.094	€ 883	€ 978
Catégorie II - revenus moyens		2.282	€ 3.872.799	€ 1.697	€ 1.119	€ 1.135
Catégorie III - faibles revenus		5.549	€ 14.485.034	€ 2.610	€ 2.375	€ 2.234
Total		11.937	€ 22.851.772	€ 1.801	€ 1.574	€ 1.581

Figure 52 Evolution in the number and amount of energy premiums granted to households by income category between 2020 and 2022 (Bruxelles Environnement, 2023)

Despite the efforts undertaken by the region to promote access to energy bonuses for several target groups, some believe that certain segments of the Brussels population still benefit too little from these bonuses. Some actors indeed suggest that these subsidies remain difficult to access for people in poverty, thus generating socially regressive effects, such as the so-called '**Matthieu effects**'²⁶ (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale, 2019). Several factors contribute to explaining the lower recourse of loss well-off populations to renovation subsidies. They include notably the previously mentioned **large proportion of tenants among these populations and the associated lack of ability of the latter to undertake renovations in their housing**. Besides the status of tenants,

²⁶ The Belgian Combat Poverty Service, which denounces 'Matthew effects', defines them as "regressive distribution effects [applying] to policy measures that are systematically used more by wealthier population groups, while they are used less - or not at all - by people experiencing poverty" (Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale 2023, p. 6).

other factors also reduce access to renovation grants for less well-off households, including the **lack of capacity to pre-finance the renovation work**, the **insufficient amount of subsidies**, the **limited access to information and assistance on technical, organizational, and financial aspects of a renovation (which is notably linked with the fragmentation of supports)**, and the **non-take-up of right effect** (ICEDD et al. 2019 ; Financité, 2019 ; Service de lutte contre la pauvreté, la précarité et l'exclusion sociale, 2019, Vanhille et al. 2017).

Besides 'Matthieu effects', the energy renovation subsidies can also generate other types of socially regressive effects. Deep home renovations carried out by landlords with these subsidies can, indeed, also have negative impacts on low-income tenants, as explained by von Platten and colleagues: "It has been well-documented that value-adding energy retrofitting can – sometimes even intentionally by the landlord – cause economic and social consequences for tenants, with examples such as displacement, sometimes referred to as **'renoviction'**, and economic distress caused by increased rents" (von Platten et al. 2020, p.2). Several empirical research actually show that energy refurbishment policies can foster speculation, rents increase, which can lead to energy-efficiency-related 'renoviction' – i.e.: the eviction of populations due to the demolition of their housing or rents that have become unaffordable in the context of landlord-led energy renovation projects – and resulting "low-carbon gentrification" (von Platten et al., 2020 ; Grossmann, 2019 ; Bouzarovsky et al., 2018 ; Femenías et al., 2018 ; Mangold et al., 2016 ; Grossmann et Huning, 2015). Such processes can combine with – and be reinforced by – other ecological gentrification processes linked with energy renovation of commercial buildings (Chegut et al., 2014) or urban greening projects developed as part of biodiversity conservation or climate change adaptation strategies (Immergluck and Balan, 2018; Haase et al., 2017).

Although, to our knowledge, no research has yet objectivized the 'renoviction' phenomenon associated with energy renovation subsidies in the BCR, this issue was raised repeatedly during the interviews and workshop we conducted. In addition, the phenomenon is recognized by Brussels' Gouvernement as a key risk to be prevented in its Air Climate Energy Plan (PACE), which states that "the measures proposed in PACE must not contribute to the phenomenon of "renoviction", which is observed in old or working-class neighborhoods that have been extensively renovated" (Bruxelles Environnement 2023, p. 169). This plan actually provides for a strengthening of housing renovation policies, notably with the establishment of a progressive **obligation to renovate energy-inefficient housing**²⁷ from 2033, which increases the risk of 'renoviction'. This measure could generate 'renoviction' phenomena among tenants, but also among owners who would not have the capacity to renovate their homes. According to an expert interviewed, the renovation obligation could indeed force certain owners to sell their homes, which could lead to a concentration of property in the hands of a few owners and potentially to a worsening of the increase in rents in the BCR. In the PACE, the regional government is committed to implement several measures to prevent the risk of 'renoviction', and notably to "grant premiums or surcharges to landlords on condition that they comply with a rent agreement" (Ibidem, p. 170). However, it seems, according to some actors and experts, that these measures, which are not very coercive, will not be sufficient to prevent the risk of renoviction and a worsening of the affordable housing crisis in Brussels.

In addition to the future obligation for energy renovation of housing in Brussels provided for by PACE, the **extension of the European Emissions Trading System (ETS) system to GHG of buildings** from 2025 also threatens certain segments of the Brussels population. This measure should indeed lead to an increase fossil fuel prices for residential energy use, which could affect certain vulnerable households and aggravate the problem of energy poverty mentioned above (see section 4.2.4). In order to prevent such socially regressive effect, the EU has planned to financially support Member States in

²⁷ The PACE provides for the obligation to renovate 'energy leaky houses', i.e.: PEB F and G buildings, in 2033 and PEB D and E building in 2045.

implementing measures targeting vulnerable social groups by allocating them, through the Social Climate Fund, a share of the revenues from the auctioning of emission allowances under the new ETS system. To obtain these funds, Member States must develop National Social Climate Plans in which they specify the measures they will implement to prevent the negative distributional impacts of the extension of ETS system. The development of these plans has just been started by the different regions in Belgium. The measures planned by the BCR to address the potential negative impacts of the ETS on vulnerable households are therefore not yet known.

Finally, it seems important to mention the limits of the **Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) standards**, which some describe as unfair and ineffective in really reducing consumption (see for e.g., von Platten et al., 2020). Indeed, by only considering the quantity of energy spent per square meter without integrating the size of the home, this label penalizes small homes compared to large ones. Yet, as mentioned previously (see section 4.2.5), size is one of the factors that most influence the energy consumption of housing.

4.2.8. Unequal Exposure to Climate Risks in Housing

Due to the preexisting inequalities in the housing sector, the poorest households bear not only more the burden of climate actions, but also that of inactions. They are indeed more likely to suffer from the impacts of climate change on their living space than wealthier households. In many European countries, poor households tend to live in dense urban areas, places that are more exposed to climate risks, such as flooding or heat islands (Ludden et al., 2022; European Environment Agency, 2020). Recent research has revealed that this correlation between low income, density and exposure to climatic/environmental risks is also observed at the scale of the Brussels Capital Region (De Muynck et al., forthcoming) (see Figure 53). The poor households are all the more exposed to heat wave since they live in houses that are, as stated above, less well insulated (see section 4.2.2). This means not only the location of their own dwelling but also its quality makes the least advantaged households more vulnerable to the effects of a changing climate. Poor households are even more vulnerable to climate risks, because they have less capacity to afford home renovation works that could reduce their exposure to future climate risks (see sections 4.2.6), less chance of having home content insurance, and less access to information on the climate-related hazards. In addition, the disadvantaged households are more sensitive to climate risks due to poorer than average health status (Ludden et al., 2022; European Environment Agency, 2020). Besides socio-economically disadvantaged people, elderly people are also particularly vulnerable to climate risks.

Figure 53 Summary map of environmental risks (soil pollution, heat islands, air pollution, noise, flood risk) in Brussels (left) and map of median incomes by statistical sector in Brussels in 2017 (right) (De Muynck 2021, p. 13)

In the future, the effects of climate change are expected to intensify, so do the magnitude and frequency of climate risks (De Troch, 2019). The future evolution of inequalities in exposure to climate risk will depend on the extent of **global climate change**²⁸ and the **adaptation policies** implemented by the BCR.

4.2.9. Unequal Access to Information, Decision-Making, Civic Space and Courts on Climate-Energy Issues in Housing

Inequalities in participation in policy- and decision-making processes on climate and energy issues are difficult to document, since there is currently little data on these issues in the BCR.

In the literature, several authors highlight the non-involvement of representatives of vulnerable groups in the elaboration and implementation of low-carbon transition policies in housing and resulting lack of recognition of the specific needs of these social groups (Grossmann 2019; Bouzarovsky et al., 2018). In this regard, Grossmann explains that “*decisions are designed and implemented by experts (mostly with a background in economics and law), together with politicians, not to mention the influence of lobby groups. Representatives or advocates of vulnerable groups were not included.*” (Grossmann 2019, p.155). This echoes certain statements collected during the interviews and workshops that we organized. Some experts and actors have indeed evoked the inequalities in the sphere of influence of public policies, pointing the lack of representative and effective participation in housing and city policies, especially of most precarious people. An expert has further explained that there is usually no or late consultation of representative of persons experiencing precarity or poverty in decision- and policy-making processes on energy issues. They state that energy market actors are, for their part, involved much further upstream and with greater influence in the elaboration and implementation of energy policy. In this regard, they deplore the over-representation of technicians and economists in energy policy processes associated with a **depoliticization of energy issues**, which are treated as technical matter. In the same vein, other experts and actors have mentioned the higher weight of property owners in decision-making on housing policies in the BCR.

Finally, an expert interviewed also pointed out inequalities in the use of the right to take legal action. They explain that many tenants experiencing problems in housing, such as unsanitary housing, excessive rent, or non-regularization by the owner of energy provisions, do not assert their rights in

²⁸ Climate change scenarios for BCR are explored in more detail in the variable sheet devoted to climate change

court. Various factors contribute to this, including the fear of eviction or reprisals from the landlord associate with **power asymmetries between landlords and tenants**, the opacity of consumer rights linked to the **complexity of legislation in a multi-level context**, and the **lack of information** about it.

4.3. Mobility

Finally, we consider the preexisting social inequalities in the mobility sector, especially in daily mobility in Brussels and the surrounding area.

Travel is not an end in itself, but serves as an intermediary to access different economic and social activities according to different lifestyles and social constraints. For example, the fact that people travel a lot can be explained by urban sprawl and the wide spatial dispersion of activities, or by the level of the financial resources. Similarly, a low level of travel can be explained by limited financial resources or a lifestyle that allows it (for example organized around close relationships) (Chollet et al. 2005)

Urban planning and housing policies have significantly shaped mobility inequality trends in Brussels. Researchers have analyzed the interdependent impacts of urban sprawl, increasing reliance on private vehicles, and housing market dynamics on transportation access disparities. Overall, the most important issue to understand a whole range of mobility inequalities is the predominance of car use. This legacy of the "car as king" has structured the BCR, from its built environment to its economic activities, via public services, social policies and the development of public transport.

The following sections outline the main inequalities with regards to mobility in the BCR. We focus on those inequalities that are most relevant when considering the transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience.

4.3.1 Unequal Access to Mobility

The first and main set of inequalities concern the unequal access to mobility. Accessibility is defined as the ease of getting from one part of the city to another and includes as well physical accessibility to infrastructures and vehicles. Indeed, not all Brussels inhabitants have the same « right » to mobility. Some of these differences can be attributed to their socio-economic characteristics such as age, gender, occupation, income and place of living. Several analyses point to increasing socioeconomic divides and spatial segregation tied to mobility within Brussels since the 1980s. At a regional level, researchers characterize Brussels as consolidating over recent decades into a "poor crescent" surrounded by a prosperous hinterland. Within the city itself, lower income populations concentrate in particular areas while facing declining mobility access (Toint et al., 2011; Van Crieckingen, 2008; Strale 2019).

This unequal access to mobility is closely linked to unequal access to the region's regional and extra-regional resources, as a result of an unequal distribution of accessibility, which itself is induced by multidimensional factors: individual (physical, socio-economic conditions, family constraints), contextual (proximity to services, facilities, leisure areas, accessibility of the region by public transport, quality of pedestrian and cycle infrastructure), distributive (distribution of public resources). These differentiated levels of accessibility are themselves inextricably linked to the type of activity and lifestyle that individuals wish to pursue (personal aspirations). Levels of accessibility and types of aspiration are themselves strongly shaped by the car and the whole system it implies and reproduces (roads, connectivity, etc.). In the following subsections, we look more specifically at the different aspects of accessibility: modal choices, transport modes (car, public transport and bike), housing and the importance of connectivity.

a) Unequal access to modal choices

As income rises, mobility choices diversify. Inequalities appear first in terms of daily mobility indicators (number of journeys, distance, time), then in terms of access to private cars. Modal choices vary according to age, reason for travel, resources, but also place of residence... The more central the location, the more attractive the public transport offer; on the contrary, the more peripheral the location, the more the private car will be considered the most efficient alternative. Modal choices are as well explained by differentiated socialisation to mobility according to gender, income and education. Indeed better education favors understanding and the use of the different transport modes, linking and combining them: mobility is complex and there are numerous operators. Lack of education can prevent people from knowing their rights, for example access to preferential STIB fares.

b) Unequal access to car

In Brussels, household car ownership rates have declined and are now significantly lower than in the rest of the country and the periphery. This fall in car ownership has been accompanied by a drastic reduction in the modal share of the car. Yet, this reduction does not lead to a similar reduction in the number of cars on the road (since the population has increased significantly), or in the distances travelled (Hubert et al. 2013). In terms of inequalities, not owning a car is an obstacle to accessing destinations that are poorly served by public transport, at certain times (e.g. evenings or weekends), and accompanied by young children. Conversely, owning a car puts a strain on the budget of many disadvantaged households (ibid).

The spatial marginalization of lower income populations resulting from urban sprawl contributes to dependence on private vehicles for suburban commuters across socioeconomic strata (Toint et al., 2011; Boussauw et al., 2017).

Moreover, access to a car may be necessary for certain workers whose car is a work tool (shopkeepers who collect their products themselves, for example) who are often already the most disadvantaged. In the current mobility context, not having a car makes access to education, work and leisure spaces more difficult, as such de-motorisation have unequal impacts. For example, less qualified jobs are less accessible by public transport. On the contrary well-paid jobs tend to be localised in the center of Brussels.

Figure 54 displays statistics from Statbel (2019) suggesting that, while the number of cars owned per household increases with income with the BCR, the proportion of poor suburban households who own a car is significantly higher. It suggests that reliance on private automobiles intersects with socioeconomic inequality. Due to high purchase and operating costs, low-income populations may own cars at disproportionately lower rates. This dynamic concentrates connectivity disadvantages with groups already facing economic marginalization.

Figure 54 Number of cars owned per monthly income, in Brussels and its periphery.

In Figure 55, Strale (2017) shows inequalities in car ownership within Brussels confirming that within the BCR, there are relatively more car owners in relatively wealthier municipalities of Brussels.

Qui possède une voiture et qui paye le parking à Bruxelles?

Figure 55 Spatial distribution of car ownership, paid parking, and income in Brussels (2015). Source: Strale (2017)

Overall, urban sprawl heightens dependence on private vehicles across socioeconomic groups, but the necessity of automobile ownership disproportionately harms low-income populations through mobility restrictions and related constraints to accessing housing, jobs and services. Consequently, the outsized reliance on cars and resulting traffic emissions intensifies mobility inequality for those without reliable automobile access.

Another important inequality related to car access are the company cars. The company car system benefits workers on the highest incomes (Figure 56), and only 25% of company cars were used by women in 2010 (May et al. 2019). The majority of company car owners live on the outskirts of towns, in residential areas with dispersed housing which encourages increased car use (ibid). Furthermore, the use of a company car increases the number of cars in the household (ibid).

Figure 56 Distribution of company cars by income decile (Belgium, 2013) (May et al. 2019)

There has been a decrease in car ownership and the number of cars in Brussels. This decline does not equally affect all socio-economic groups, as it disproportionately impacts lower-income households. This is compounded by the increasing cost of housing in Brussels, which affects the budget families can allocate to mobility, including car ownership.

c) Unequal access to good public transport

Although the urban public transport network in Brussels is well developed overall, there are several journeys for which it remains ineffective: cross-town journeys, east-west traffic in the canal zone and access to employment areas located on the edge of the region or further away in the metropolitan area (Hubert et al. 2013).

Accessibility through public transport generally follows a concentric pattern, with those furthest from the centre having less access (see Figure 57). Lebrun (2018) shows that nearly 30% of the population of Brussels currently lives in neighbourhoods that, because of their location, are inaccessible with public transport to important work, commercial, cultural, educational and health hubs. And almost 10% of Brussels residents (112000) live more than 40 minutes away on average from business centres.

Figure 57 Hourly access to activity hubs by the STIB according to median time in the morning rush hour, on a working day (Lebrun 2018)

Lebrun's study (2018) shows that the contrasting geography of accessibility between neighbourhoods contrasts the efficiency of underground networks (metro) with the poorer performance of neighbourhoods served only by surface services (tram and bus). Indeed, road traffic conditions (congestion) have a negative impact on the accessibility of neighbourhoods because traffic congestion has a major impact on public transport performance.

Toint et al. (2011) note that urban sprawl in Belgium pushes young couples to live further from city centers but finds poorer residents lack the private vehicle access to commute effectively. With lower car ownership rates, these households depend more heavily on public transit while often residing in relatively disconnected neighborhoods. Fronteddu (2021) reports low-income populations in Brussels take fewer trips annually than wealthier residents.

Researchers emphasize that mobility inequality issues in Brussels stem from the interdependence of multiple systemic factors across domains including infrastructure, transportation networks, urban morphology, and governance (Strale 2019). Public transport, while experiencing an uptick in the modal share and overall journey count (Hubert et al., 2013), is still subject to a variety of influencing factors. There is a pronounced geographical split in how public transport is utilized (Strale 2019).

Boussauw and Vanoutrive (2017) and Strale (2019) argue that common technocratic transport policy debates concerning congestion and transit capacity overlook these complex, interconnected dynamics that shape accessibility.

d) Unequal access to bike and active mobility

This unequal access to mobility increases with regards to active and more sustainable mobility such as biking. The low socio-economic level, but also the lack of space in Brussels homes and cultural obstacles, explain the low rate of bicycle ownership in Brussels (39.9% of households) compared to the periphery (74.8%) (Hubert et al. 2013). There is an over-representation of people with higher education qualifications among cyclists, with 92% of cyclists claiming to have a higher education qualification (PorVélo 2023). Income, gender, culture (for example the social prestige to own a car, the elitism of biking culture) and age increase barriers. The lack of feeling of security can be another barrier to use bikes (as well as shared cars).

Distributive inequalities manifest physically through uneven distribution of sustainable mobility infrastructure across communities. For example, analyses show lower income neighborhoods often lack access to cycling paths, bike shares, pedestrian facilities and public transit connections (Ermans, personal communication, 2023). This infrastructure bias limits realistic mobility options for disadvantaged groups. For example, due to the inequality in the ownership and use of electric bikes, speed pedelecs, longtails, cargo bikes and related infrastructures. The increasing use of electric bikes is ambivalent : it decreases some inequalities (gender, age and physical condition) while it increases others (financial, reparability). Even regarding “soft mobility”, speed has become a factor of exclusion (Luppari, personal communication, 2023). In addition, the digital divide accentuates inequalities by slowing down access to new modes of transport.

The housing structure makes it more difficult for the poor crescent’s inhabitants to use bikes (less parking and storage space). Further, there is an unequal access to places of residence where there are many public and local services and where there are many good-quality cycle infrastructures.

Despite these barriers to bike use, there has been a constant increase of its use in Brussels since 2010 and the average annual growth rate since 2010 has been around 12.6% (ProVélo 2023). Interestingly, there has a reduction in the number of children riding their own bikes (ibid) which can be explained by the increased use of cargo bikes.

The walking infrastructure is not suitable for everyone, especially people with reduced mobility or visual disabilities, old people.

e) Lack of connectivity

Connectivity (transport links between urban and peri-urban areas that are convenient for their inhabitants) is unequally distributed. Connectivity gaps tied to both public and private transportation options contribute significantly to mobility inequality between poorer and more affluent areas (Toint et al, 2009; Fronteddu 2021). Connecting the different parts of the city better is a major challenge in Brussels, as many journeys remain difficult, even between neighbouring districts (for example, between Forest and Anderlecht or between Laeken and Evere). This lack of connectivity particularly penalises those without a car. (Hubert et al. 2013)

Strale (2019) notes that disparities in connectivity and accessibility between municipalities and neighborhoods drive broader socio-spatial segregation. Due to the continuous expansion of urban areas and increasing congestion, there has been a noticeable rise in both the length and duration of journeys on the road.

Strale (2019) cites gaps in integration of public transport networks and lack of a coherent metropolitan mobility strategy as key barriers to connectivity. Concentrated infrastructure investments in wealthier municipalities combined with uneven transit supply between neighborhoods entrench divergence.

Strale (2019) details substantial mobility connectivity gaps between various districts of Brussels and its hinterland across multiple transportation modes. Using a mixed quantitative and qualitative approach, Strale categorizes metropolitan Brussels into four distinct types of outskirts based primarily on mobility capacity:

- Nearby car outskirts: Heavily car dependent and lacking public transit but with reasonable highway access and limited congestion.
- Well-connected outskirts: Quality road and rail connections to Brussels but very congested
- Remote car outskirts: High car use out of necessity given sparse population and negligible public transportation.
- Remote poorly connected outskirts: Forced reliance on infrequent and inefficient transit.

This typology demonstrates systemic mobility connectivity divides. The structural factors co-producing these disparities across political, environmental and socioeconomic realms severely restrict transport accessibility for many communities.

It shows that the relationship between social-ecological inequalities and mobility is complex.

f) Unequal access to housing

Research demonstrates that equitable access to affordable, quality housing represents a central determinant of mobility capacity and associated opportunity in Brussels (Ermans, personal communication, 2023). Housing conditions and location dictate accessibility to jobs, services and sustainable transportation options. Yet socioeconomic inequality manifests clearly through disparities in living standards that constrain mobility.

Housing is crucial in influencing mobility-related inequality (Ermans personal communication, 2023). First and foremost, a residence's proximity to essential destinations and public transit infrastructure defines transport accessibility irrespective of social status. Unequal access to modal choices and transport modes is inextricably linked to unequal access to housing, a direct consequence to urban sprawl. Significant patterns of socioeconomic division are present in and around Brussels, manifesting at both the broader regional scale and the local level (Costa and Valk, 2021). Several studies point to urban sprawl trends that push residents further away from Brussels city center as both cause and consequence of mobility inequalities (Toint et al., 2011; Boussauw and Vanoutrive, 2017; Halleux, 2005).

As higher income households move to larger single-family homes in suburban neighborhoods, lower income groups concentrate in deteriorating inner-city housing. High land prices in cities push young families to move to the outskirts, contributing to urban sprawl. However, outlying areas with more affordable development often lack connectivity via public transit or safe cycling infrastructure. Urban sprawl leads to changes in modal split, resulting in increased use of private transport for daily trips such as home-work/school, shopping, and leisure (Toint et al., 2011). As families get cars, they can live in cheaper areas outside the city, which makes the city grow in size. Easier travel and car use have led to people living further apart, causing cities to spread out more (Halleux, 2005).

Van Crielingen (2008) shows that gentrification in historically working-class central neighborhoods also displaces lower income residents towards cheaper peripheral areas with poorer connectivity. It suggests that sprawl encourages car-dependent suburbanization that can exclude poorer households without vehicles while increasing per capita transport emissions. Gentrification trends in Brussels appear to increase price and push lower income residents out of well-connected neighborhoods. Resulting displacement to more remote locales with substandard connectivity exacerbates mobility inequality (Ermans, personal communication, 2023).

Beyond location, qualitative factors related to housing also prove critical. For example, apartment size and design facilitate or deter ownership and storage of car-free mobility options like bicycles. If buildings lack adequate parking or charging facilities for electric vehicles as well, the appeal of these sustainable transport modes diminishes regardless of resident financial resources.

In other words, analyses clearly tie Brussels' physical expansion to mobility inequality formation, particularly through intersecting housing and transportation access barriers for disadvantaged communities spatially marginalized to poorer connected peripheries.

4.3.2 Unequal Impact of Mobility Policies

There are various quantitative and qualitative effects of transport policies on the mobility practices of the most disadvantaged people. The long-lasting effect of « car as king » approach and its subsequent policies and measures has structured the territory in term of housing (urban sprawl), infrastructure (roads, parking space) and public transport (under-financed). Another aspect is the strong focus of mobility policies on commuting journeys. Even if the inhabitants of deprived inner-city areas have access to good coverage by the public transport network, the timetables and the type of journey encouraged by mobility policies (always the home-work commute) do not favor them because the most precarious jobs are located outside the network and occur outside the timetables. Similarly, road infrastructures favor the fluidity of the commute journeys. In new redevelopment projects maintaining flow capacity is still often the guiding principle.

Yet, researchers have shown that sustainable mobility and associated environmental policies in Brussels have often failed to achieve sustainability and equity aims, instead exacerbating inequality due to disparate socioeconomic impacts (Boussauw et al., 2017; Fronteddu, 2021). Intended improvements frequently generate unintended consequences that disproportionately affect disadvantaged groups who lack resources to adapt.

a) Company cars

Among the policies with the greatest impact, and as mentioned above, the measures allowing access to company cars are unfair on several levels (accessibility, contribution and impacts of environmental degradation). Despite growing criticism for their fiscal and environmental costs, the number of company cars and households with access to them is increasing. This trend is driven by the tax benefits it offers to both employers and employees, rather than environmental concerns (Ermans, personal communication 2023). Such pro company car policies are contributing to climate change and air pollution, particularly because many company cars are diesel-powered. Although there is a shift towards electrification of the company car fleet, he remains skeptical about the environmental benefits, especially compared to gasoline vehicles. Fronteddu's (2021) equity analysis further articulates the regressive effects of recent Brussels mobility policies. Tax incentives around company cars, which studies show increase congestion and emissions, predominantly benefit higher earning employees. And proposed congestion pricing regimes risk further restricting mobility access for marginalized communities without improving alternative options.

b) Car restricting measures

Other recent mobility policies restricting car use such as Good Move and the LEZ have unequal impacts and risk reinforcing social inequalities. Indeed, car restrictions impact housing prices: improved quality of life in neighborhoods with less traffic increases housing prices. In Brussels, as the city moves towards making car travel less feasible, a person's location, especially proximity to metro stations or living in dense urban areas, becomes crucial for mobility.

Mobility policy interventions intended to advance sustainability goals often overlook implications for socioeconomic equity, as evidenced by recent studies on Brussels' low emission zone (LEZ) implementation (Verbeek & Hincks, 2022). LEZs emerge from growing recognition of the public health threats posed by transport emissions, with air pollution burdens falling disproportionately on disadvantaged communities (Clark et al., 2014; Hajat et al., 2015). However, by restricting the most polluting vehicles, LEZs also raise social justice debates around impacts on accessibility. Indeed, the Brussels low emission zone banning older high pollution vehicles from downtown disproportionately impacted lower income families unable to upgrade cars (Boussauw and Vanoutrive 2017)

Another emblematic car restriction measure is the creation of a new vast pedestrian zone in the centre of Brussels, a neighborhood populated with working-class and diverse population, yet going through gentrification pressure that is likely to increase with such a project (Kebrowski et al. 2019).

c) public transport policies

Boussauw and Vanoutrive (2017) employ several case studies to demonstrate that sustainability focused mobility planning initiatives counterproductively increased social divides. For example, subsidies meant to incentivize public transit over private car use had the unintended impact of increasing overall travel. Wealthier citizens took advantage of discounted fares to simply make more trips, heightening congestion and emissions.

Strale (2017) also critiques mobility policy impacts on vulnerable groups, arguing that public transit fare increases exceed both inflation and average household income growth rates. This dynamic exacerbates mobility inequality given lower income residents' reliance on public transport options.

4.3.3 Unequal Contribution to Environmental Degradation

Brussels households do not contribute equally to environmental degradation. In particular, company cars beneficiaries are important contributors of commuting journeys. They use cars more and car-share less. They travel longer distance too (Figure 58). Almost a third of the car traffic generated by people travelling to, from or within Brussels is made up of company cars (May et al. 2019).

Figure 58 Comparison of annual kilometres travelled by company cars and private cars (Belgium) (May et al. 2019)

The electrification of the car fleet that is put forward as a solution raises questions in term of climate impacts. While it might indeed improve locally air quality, an electric car emits greenhouse gases, the impact of which is directly proportional to the mass and size of the battery, and needs critical materials such as lithium, cobalt and rare earth.

4.3.4 Unequal Impacts of Environmental Damage and Risks

a) Unequal impact on environment and health

Road transport is responsible for emissions of atmospheric pollutants that affect air quality. There are two types of emissions:

- Car exhaust gases contain substances such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), fine particles (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, Black Carbon), sulphur oxides (SO_x), carbon monoxide (CO) and several heavy metals. These emissions vary according to the type of fuel and the EURO standard (and age) of the vehicle.

- Abrasion of tyres, brakes and road surfaces is a source of emissions of fine particles and heavy metals, which vary according to the weight of the vehicle.

In Brussels, road transport is one of the main sources of emissions of acidifying substances, ozone precursors - including nitrogen oxides (NO_x) - and fine particles (see Figure 59). These emissions have a negative impact on air quality and cause health problems for inhabitants. Yet, researchers have shown that pollution due to car traffic is higher in deprived neighborhoods, where residents have nonetheless fewer cars. These neighborhoods are more vulnerable to climate change. Transport related air pollution concentrates in poorer neighborhoods across the city's "poor crescent" perversely compounding environmental and health impacts. There is a similar inequality in noise pollution generated by road traffic. There is finally an unequal exposure to aircraft overflights in Brussels.

Concentration de NO₂ à Bruxelles (2021 : Curieuzenair)

Figure 59 NO₂ concentration in Brussels

Verbeek and Hincks' (2022) analysis explores these tensions by mapping associations between income, emissions exposure, vehicle compliance rates, and transit access across Brussels neighborhoods. Findings reveal the highest inequality in exposure manifesting in a ring just beyond the current LEZ boundaries, predominantly impacting lower income areas. However, these exposed communities also exhibit higher non-compliant vehicle ownership rates as well as better public transportation connectivity. Therefore, while Brussels LEZ appears well designed to reduce environmental health

inequalities, its geographic coverage paradoxically overlooks some highly unequal exposure zones (Verbeek & Hincks, 2022).

Traffic circulation plans and public space redevelopment in Brussels improve air quality, particularly benefiting populations in more polluted, central areas. However, at a more localized level, these plans tend to reduce traffic in residential areas, which are often wealthier, while directing it towards busier roads where poorer populations reside (Ermans, personal communication, 2023). This situation leads to a nuanced impact on socio-economic inequalities, where the benefits of reduced traffic and improved air quality are not evenly distributed across different social groups and neighborhoods. Haut du formulaire Expanding restrictions aided by tailored mobility support policies could enable further synchronized emissions and social equity improvements. Overall, the LEZ example highlights the need for integrated policy assessments blending distributional equity considerations across economic and environmental realms to ensure just mobility transitions.

There are as well the damages and risks related to car traffic (accidents and public space use) which is unequally distributed and affect people differently according to their gender, age and income. But other species are as well impacted by car traffic as outline in section 4.1.6. (Lack of consideration for non-humans in urban planning).

b) Unequal access to public space

An inequality exists with regards to public space's access and use. The use of car is dominant compared to other transport modes and children are the main « victims » of this configuration. There is an unequal access to qualitative public space. Many parked and therefore unused vehicles occupy public space.

There has been like in many other cities a reduction of the space allocated to cars in public areas, making it increasingly difficult to own and park a car. This change, while environmentally motivated, unintentionally exacerbates socio-economic inequalities as wealthier individuals are more likely to afford private parking, bypassing the reduction in public parking spaces (Ermans, personal communication 2023).

4.3.5 Unequal Access to Participation, Contribution to Policies and Political / Collective Action

A final set of inequalities exists with regard to residents' access to mobility policies themselves and the extent to which they have a say in them. These inequalities are rooted in the various “uneven socio-spatial relations and power dynamics that shape urban transport” (Kebrowski et al. 2019, 16). Procedural inequalities exacerbate socio-spatial segregation by excluding some people from planning and policy-making processes.

a) Unequal access to representativity

Despite the fact that the places of residence of elected representatives are increasingly similar to those of the population as a whole, researchers show that the most affluent neighbourhoods continue to be over-represented (Vandermotten 2021) (Figure 60). Recognition-based inequalities explain mobility inequalities where policy-makers and leaders fail to recognize the distinct needs of different social groups based on factors such as income, language, ability and age. This often results in stereotyping and rejection of the legitimate mobility rights of peripheral and dependent communities. There is an issue with regards to representativity bias of decision-makers. Indeed, marginalized populations frequently lack representation in key urban development and transport planning forums (Boussauw et al., 2017). With their voices disregarded, resulting decisions neglect specific mobility needs. Local participatory processes are organized, but do not necessarily give rise to balanced representation or truly democratic debate (Luppari, personal communication, 2023).

Figure 60 Residential pattern of elected representatives in 2010 and 2020 (Vandermotten 2021)

b) Unequal access to participatory processes

Citizen participation can be used as a “political instrument for legitimacy-building and consensus-forcing” (Kebrowski et al. 2019, 12). To make sure citizens participate to the governance of the issues related to mobility, participatory processes must be interactive and provide a “mutual learning experience” (13). These debates must ensure that there is engagement with potential conflicts and tensions too. In the case of the pedestrian zone, researchers have shown that the inclusion of local residents in the planning process was very superficial and very limited. The participatory process was neither deliberative nor interactive (Kebrowski et al. 2019, 15). Diverging opinions were not taking into account.

c) Unequal access to (collective) action

Inequalities in terms of available resources (cultural and economic capital, social and political networks) largely explain how certain groups of people are better able to organize themselves and defend themselves against certain projects. They explain the vulnerability of people living in working-class neighborhoods to the nuisance caused by certain projects, such as the overflight of Brussels by aircraft. Indeed researchers (Dobruszkes 2008) have shown that residents living in privileged neighborhoods are much better organized than those living in working-class neighborhoods, who are absent from the protests. Unlike the peripheral districts to the north and east, which are characterized by higher standards of living, the working-class central districts of Brussels have not taken any legal action. (Figure 61). This inequality in the collective organization of local defense has led to an increase in aircraft noise affecting working-class neighborhoods.

Figure 61 Geography of claimants by legal action (by postcode) (Dobruszkes 2008)

There is as well inequality in the way collective action is taken into account. Collective action will be judged more or less positively or negatively depending on whether it is led by social groups at the top or bottom of the social ladder.

To conclude, Kebrowski et al. (2019) built a framework to analyse transport policies (table X) in relation to citizen participation. It highlights the different aspects of an unequal access to participation to transport and mobility policy-making.

Table 1 A right to the city-inspired framework for critical analysis of transport policies and practices (Kebrowski et al. 2019)

Right to the city	Transport policy
<p>Participation: Enabling appropriation and production of urban space by inhabitants</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inclusive</i>: embracing diverse actors and responding to their diverse needs and capacities • <i>Reconciling</i> institutional/top-down and non-institutional/bottom-up/elements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Deliberative</i>: providing space for conflict/dissensus and deliberation/consensus
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Interactive</i>: acknowledging the plurality of transport-related knowledge and offering all participants a mutual learning experience
<p>Power: Revealing and challenging its existing urban regimes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Redistributive</i>: transferring significant power towards city-dwellers; co-created with and by, not for them
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Political</i>: opposing de-politicised, consent-manufacturing techniques
<p>Totality: Concerning all aspects of urban society and space</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Beyond the right to mobility</i>: questioning the relationship between urbanised capitalism and transport, challenging the normative and uneven character of mobility
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Holistic and multi-scalar</i>: concerned with the whole urban society and territory, reaching beyond administrative boundaries, parochial spaces and interests
<p>Utopia: Moving towards a possible world yet to come</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Effective yet reflexive</i>: producing tangible results but avoiding the trap of providing ready-made policy solutions

5. System of Social-Ecological Inequalities in Brussels-Capital Region

5.1. Variables Influencing Social-Ecological Inequalities

The clustering of the factors identified through the retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing, and mobility in BCR enabled us to define the following list of system variables (Table 2). This list includes **22 variables**, a definition of which is given in the table below. The list of variables is the fruit of iterative work and has evolved continuously over the months during which the prospective diagnosis has been carried out. It cannot be ruled out that the list will continue to evolve during the construction phase of the just transition scenarios.

Table 2. Definition of the variables influencing social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures, housing and mobility

	VARIABLES	DEFINITION
1	Social imaginaries	Social imaginaries are collectively held and shared understandings of the world and its social order.
2	Economic system	Economic system refers to the method of organizing production, distribution and consumption activities of goods, services and resources in place within a society. It includes notably the role of the market and private players in driving the economy, the status of property, and the pursuit of social good or profits.
3	Place of technology in society	Place of technology in society refers to our use of technology, including how often and for what purposes we leverage different technologies, and its impact on jobs (e.g. via automation) and access to public services.
4	Demographics	Demographics refers to the characteristics of the population such as its growth at the regional scale, in and out-flows, and age structure.
5	Climate change	Climate change refers to “a change in the state of the climate that can be identified (e.g., by using statistical tests) by changes in the mean and/or the variability of its properties and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer. Climate change may be due to natural internal processes or external forcings such as modulations of the solar cycles, volcanic eruptions and persistent anthropogenic changes in the composition of the atmosphere or in land use.” (IPCC, 2018)
6	Economic situation of the BCR	The economic situation of the BCR refers to the state of the economy. It looks at the share of the different sectors in regional economic activity, the organisation of industry and trade, the unemployment rate, growth, inflation, and debt.
7	Urban form	Urban form refers to the physical elements that structure and shape the city, in particular the occupation of public space, the organisation of green spaces, urbanisation processes or soil sealing. It also includes the natural base on which the city is built (the various river basins, for example).
8	Quality of the environment	The quality of the environment is defined by the properties and characteristics of the environment at different levels (air, noise, etc.) and their impact on human beings (e.g. health) and other species. It is also characterised by the way it is experienced and perceived by different social groups according to their class, race, gender, etc.

9	Politics	Politics is a dimension of governance characterized by the range of concerned actors and different power relations between them. The actors can be public (political and administrative authorities) or private (such as civil society organizations, employers' federations, workers' unions or citizens).
10	State of the public finances	The state of the public finance refers to the budget (resources and expenditures) that is established on annual basis by the regional government. It concerns the various public funding streams and investments strategies and decisions by the BCR and its hinterland.
11	State structure	The state structure refers to the division of competencies between different levels of power (e.g., municipal, regional, and referral) and between policy domains within a given level of power (energy, housing, climate).
12	Modes of public action	Modes of public action refer to the different ideas and norms that underpin policy objectives, the types of instruments used, and the way in which policy issues are defined and understood.
13	Land use planning	Land use planning refers to the measures that regulate the land and its use, including ownership.
14	Social security system	Social security refers to collectively recognised redistribution mechanisms that guarantee financial support for everyone at specific times or for specific needs (old age, unemployment, disability, healthcare, children).
15	State of the energy market	The state of the energy market is characterized by energy actors and structure, demand and offer for the different energy vectors (electricity, natural gas, oil...) as well as prices for these different vectors.
16	State of the housing market	The state of the housing market is characterized by housing actors and structure, housing demand and offer in the different market segments (sales, private rental, and public rental), housing price, and distribution of population by tenure status.
17	Socio-economic situation of households	The socio-economic situation of households encompasses their income, level of education, quality of life and associated opportunities and privileges.
18	Spatial distribution of social groups	The spatial distribution of social groups refers to the diversity in the BCR, including the different cultural and religious identities, the different languages spoken, alongside the spatial concentration of different national, ethnic and cultural groups, which is today characterised by segregation.
19	Economic activities of people	Economic activities of people refer to the activities of inhabitants of the BCR and its hinterland that lead to goods manufacture or services provision. It includes as well unpaid activities such as domestic or care work.
20	Mobility policy	Mobility policy refers to the actions of government, including legislation and program delivery, which have a direct or indirect impact on mobility equipment (public transport), infrastructures (public space and roads) and traveling habits of inhabitants.
21	Greening policy	Greening policy refers to the actions of government, including legislation and program delivery, which have a direct or indirect impact on creating and maintaining green infrastructure in urban areas.

22	Housing policy	Housing policy refers to the actions of government, including legislation and program delivery, which have a direct or indirect impact on housing supply and availability, housing standards and urban planning.
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For each of these variables, we have developed ‘variable sheet’. These sheets present a brief retrospective analysis of the variables, which aim at informing the scenario-building process. An example of ‘variable sheet’ is provided in appendix 6.

5.2. Analysis of Relationships between System Variables

To understand the positioning of the factors influencing social-ecological inequalities and their relationships, we have developed a visual representation of each sub-system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR by combining two complementary tools: the prospective radar and the causal loop diagram. To provide an understanding of what the prospective radar looks like, an example of the prospective radar for green Infrastructure sub-system can be found in Fig. 57. The interactive Miro board, presenting all three sub-systems in higher resolution, can be found [here](#). The central area of the radar (in red) encompasses the heart of the system, capturing the main social-ecological inequalities that exist in the sub-system of study. Factors in the second level, in the orange space of the radar, directly influence the inequalities at the heart of the system, while those in the yellow zone indirectly influence the inequalities at the heart of the system. In the case of social-ecological inequalities in urban green infrastructure (which have been extensively detailed in section 4.1), direct factors include for instance soil sealing, urban plans and tools, fragmentation of green spaces, and misrepresentation in participation. Indirect factors include the non-regulation of the housing market, anthropocentrism as a guiding paradigm, air, soil, and noise pollution, and past urbanization processes, to name a few.

Figure 63 Simplified representation of the system of social-ecological inequalities in the BCR

An initial analysis of the similarities and disparities between the three sub-systems reveals a number of interesting aspects for our diagnosis:

- First, the three sub-systems share key indirect variables such as *climate change*, *demographics* or *economic system*. This seems logical insofar as these variables are contextual or generic variables relating to more global issues that are important determinants of inequality in general.
- Second, certain variables are more relevant for one system than another. For instance, the *state of the housing market* is very influential on social-ecological inequalities in the housing sub-system, although it is also relevant to a lesser extent for green infrastructure and mobility social-ecological inequalities. Similarly, the *place of technology in society* is more relevant for the housing and mobility sub-systems than it is for the green infrastructure sub-systems. A last

example is to be found in relation to *crises*²⁹ which has proven to be much more determinant for the housing sub-system.

- Finally, while some variables are quite specific, such as *state of the housing market*, others are broader, encompassing a number of different factors specific to each sub-system. For instance, while there are many common factors within the “*social imaginaries*” variable between the sub-systems, there are also factors unique to a particular sub-system. In the mobility sub-system, the “*car-as-king*” mentality has hugely influenced mobility social-ecological inequalities in the BCR, while in the housing sub-system, the placing of private property above collective interest shapes these inequalities. In terms of urban green infrastructure, a paradigm of anthropocentric has historically shaped urban greening, and continues to strongly influence social-ecological inequalities today.

²⁹ In the end, we decided to exclude the *crises* variable from our list of system variable. Instead, the crises will be integrated into the construction of scenarios via ‘wild cards’.

6. Conclusions

To address climate change and ensure environmental sustainability while guaranteeing justice for humans and non-humans alike, we need to rapidly initiate a just transition. This just transition aims to tackle social-ecological inequalities as territories move toward resilience to climate change and a decarbonized economy. How can we effectively support the transition from a high-carbon economy based on a system that reinforces inequalities to a low-carbon model in which justice for humans and non-humans plays a central role? We need to understand the past and present situation of social-ecological inequalities and the various factors that influence them. To do this, the COGITO research project uses prospective analysis for building and analyzing scenarios for a just transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in the BCR by 2050. The first phase of this prospective research project was to map out and better comprehend social-ecological inequalities and their influencing factors. In this report, we presented our prospective diagnosis of social-ecological inequalities in relation to green infrastructure, housing and mobility in the context of the BCR.

After introducing the context and objective of the prospective diagnosis, we presented the social-ecological justice framework we used to carry-out this analysis. This framework was chosen as it allows us to combine different but equally important perspectives of the (social-)environmental and ecological justice perspectives. Indeed, while (social-)environmental justice encompasses multiple dimensions of justice for humans in relation to their environment, the ecological justice perspective recognises the interlinkage between human and non-human life and includes the needs of non-humans. The framework encompasses five types of social-ecological inequalities: 1) the unequal contribution to environmental degradation, 2) the unequal distribution of environmental goods and burdens, 3) the unequal impacts of environmental policies, 4) the unequal participation in environmental policy- and decision-making processes, and 5) the unequal recognition of the needs of vulnerable/vulnerabilized groups. It further considers these types of inequalities in relation to intergenerational, intragenerational and interspecies justice.

In the next section, we outlined our methodology, an important aspect of our work since it enabled the construction of a coherent and original prospective system. To explore social-ecological inequalities in the BCR and the factors influencing these inequalities we conducted a retrospective analysis in three selected sub-systems: green infrastructure, housing and mobility. We further worked on this retrospective analysis to develop a set of variables, each grouping together several factors influencing social-ecological inequalities. This work was first based on documentary research and exploratory interviews, before being consolidated with thematic workshops. To facilitate the analysis of the interactions between the various factors, as well as the analysis of the correspondences and differences between each sub-system, we have developed a visualization of the three sub-systems in the form of a prospective radar and a causal loop diagram. This exercise enabled us to finalize the list of variables of our system. Finally, the retrospective analysis of these variables, aimed at providing the knowledge base for the scenario-building exercise, was developed based on documentary research, supplemented by interviews with experts.

In the following section, we shared the retrospective analysis of social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructure, housing and mobility we developed. We cover in this overview the five types of social-ecological inequalities outlined by our theoretical framework. Overall, these analyses highlight the complex and multiple nature of social-ecological inequalities in these different domains, alongside their many interrelated influencing factors. In addition, the analysis revealed the very close links that exist between the three sub-systems: for example, social-ecological inequalities in access to housing have a direct impact on inequalities in access to mobility or green infrastructure. It also shows that these inequalities share common root causes. These cross-cutting analysis are explored further by analysing the relationships between variables which is presented in the next section.

In the final section, we presented the resulting system of social-ecological inequalities. We created a table summarizing the 22 system variables with their definition. Each variable is a group of factors influencing the inequalities in each of our sub-systems. This list of variables has been consolidated throughout the research process, by organizing the thematic workshops as well as regular exchanges among the researchers and it may yet evolve. The variables were organised depending on their direct or indirect influence on the system of social-ecological inequalities. Nine of them are indirectly influencing social-ecological inequalities, such as land use planning or the economic system. The other 13 such as climate change, mobility policies or the urban form of the city, are of direct influence. Finally, with the help of our prospective radar where we could visualise the different variables, we then conducted an initial analysis of interactions between variables within each sub-system and relationships between variables across sub-systems.

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Appendixes

Appendix 1. Retro-Pro prospective Interview Guide

Retrospective

1. What are, for you, the **main social-ecological inequalities** in terms of green infrastructures/housing/mobility in the Brussels Capital Region?
 - a. What about inequalities in terms **distribution / participation / recognition**?
2. How have these inequalities **evolved** over the past years? (+/- 30 years)
3. What are, for you, the **main factors/changes** that have influenced (the evolutions of) these inequalities?

Prospective

1. Over the next few years, what are the **main factors/changes** that could influence the inequalities in green infrastructures/housing/mobility in the Brussels Capital Region?
 - a. Which of these factors could have the **most impact**?
 - b. Could the **transition to carbon neutrality** influence the inequalities in green infrastructures/housing/mobility in the Brussels Capital Region? How?
 - c. Could **climate change** influence the inequalities in green infrastructures/housing/mobility in the Brussels Capital Region? How?
2. How might the **existing inequalities** in green infrastructures/housing/mobility in the Brussels Region evolve **in the next years**? Why?
 - a. What about on the **long-term** (for example, to 2050)? Why?
 - b. For you, what should be done to **reduce** these existing inequalities?
3. Do you think that **new inequalities** in terms of housing might emerge in the Brussels Region **in the next years**? Why?
 - a. What about on the **long-term** (for example, to 2050)? Why?
 - b. For you, what should be done to **prevent** these new inequalities?
4. Which **actors** should be involved in this process of reducing and preventing social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures/housing/mobility?

Identification of other persons to interview

Appendix 2. Instructions for the Thematic Workshops

Exercise 1

In your opinion, what are the main social-ecological inequalities in green infrastructures/housing/mobility in the Brussels-Capital Region?

Working groups session (40')

- Individual reflection
- Pooling of results: each member of the group presents the results of their reflection.
- Select the 6 most important inequalities in the context of the just transition to carbon neutrality and climate resilience in the Brussels-Capital Region by 2050, and transfer them to a 6-sided box.

Plenary discussion (15')

Exercise 2

In your opinion, what factors have led to the current state of inequalities identified in the previous exercise?

Working groups session (45')

- Individual reflection
 - Identify the factors (max. 10).
 - Circle the ones that seem most influential to you.
- Pooling of results: each member of the group presents the result of their reflection.
- Write each factor on a coloured post-it note and place on a timeline:
 - Yellow: Influential
 - Pink: Very influential

Plenary discussion (20')

Exercise 3

In your opinion, what would be the 3 key actions to be implemented at different levels of government to address the inequalities identified above?

Plenary session (10')

- Individual reflection
 - Identify the 3 key actions and write them on post-its.
 - Stick each post-it note in the posters corresponding to the level of power at which the action should be developed (federal, regional, local, neighbourhood).

Appendix 3. Outcomes of the Thematic Workshop on Social-Ecological Inequalities in Green Infrastructures

Exercice 1

« Quelles sont les principales inégalités sociales-écologiques en matière d'infrastructures vertes urbaines dans la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale ? »

Groupe 1

<p>Qualité</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inégalités des usages et fonctions de l'espace public Inégalités dans la qualité écologique de l'infrastructure verte (+ notions de connectivité) Inégalités environnementales qui se combinent à quelques petites parcs végétalisés Inégalités de la qualité récréative, des aménagements 	<p>Accessibilité</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> accès à l'espace public et services aux jardins privés et autres espaces + capacités d'accès selon sexe, âge, état de santé, possibilités de mobilité accès qui sera RBC et à l'infrastructure verte dans RBC - tout le monde ne peut quitter la ville
<p>Participat (Conception, définir les besoins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → intégration des habitants, femmes, enfants → intégration de collectifs → Besoins de ceux qui aimeraient fréquenter ces espaces 	<p>Sensibilisation et Connaissance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Milieu familial (conception anthropocentrique) - Milieu de scolarisation (écoles etc.) environnement & programme "école du dehors" - manque d'accès à la nature physiquement et conceptuellement dans les écoles, leurs programmes et dans l'éducation.
<p>Droits humains non humains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Droits de circulation pour tous/toutes (genres, âge, humains et non-humains, etc.) couloirs / maillages écologiques - Droit de vivre/d'être en sécurité, d'avoir un abri, de vivre dans un environnement sain, viable, et résilient 	<p>Distribution géographique inégale</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - centre-ville/périphérie ; quartiers résidentiel/ex-industriel - Ne pas limiter la nature à des espaces (parcs) - quartiers résidentiel/ex-industriel - ne pas limiter la nature à des espaces (parcs)

1. Droits humains, non-humain

- Droits de circulation pour tous/toutes (genres, âge, humains et non-humains, etc.) couloirs / maillages écologiques
- Droit de vivre/d'être en sécurité, d'avoir un abri, de vivre dans un environnement sain, viable, et résilient

2. Distribution géographique inégale

- Centre-ville/périphérie ; quartiers résidentiel/ex-industriel
- Ne pas limiter la nature à des espaces (parcs)

3. Sensibilisation et connaissance

- Milieu Familial (conception - "manque d'accès...", anthropocentrés - ex : nuisibles etc.)
- Milieu de scolarisation (écoles etc.) environnement & programme "école du dehors" - manque d'accès avec la nature physiquement et conceptuellement dans les écoles, leurs programmes et dans l'éducation.

4. Participation

- Conception, définition des besoins et notamment intégrer les besoins de ceux qui ne profitent pas dans la conception et définition des espaces verts
- Intégration des habitants, femmes, enfants ; intégration de collectifs
- Besoins de ceux qui aimeraient fréquenter ces espaces (rejoins l'idée de prendre en compte les besoins des moins "favorisés")

5. Qualité

- Inégalités dans les usages et fonctions de l'espace public ; Inégalités des qualités récréatives, les aménagements
- Inégalité dans la qualité écologique de l'infrastructure verte (+ notions de connectivité)

- Inégalités environnementales qui se combinent et quartiers pollués peu végétalisés
- 6. Accessibilité**
- Prive vs publique, ex. nonaccès aux jardins privés et autres domaines
 - Inégalités dans les capacités d'accès, selon sexe, âge, état de santé, possibilités de mobilité (accès aux transports en commun notamment pour se rendre vers la périphérie pour les grands espaces verts)
 - Accès au sein RBC et à l'infrastructure verte hors RBC : tout le monde ne peut quitter la ville

Groupe 2

INSTRUMENTALISATION DES ESPACES VERTS PAR LE MARCHÉ	DISTRIBUTION ET ACCESSIBILITÉ
POLLUTIONS (AIR, NUISANCES SONORES, SOLS...)	QUALITÉ BIOLOGIQUE
QUEL PUBLIC PREND PART À LA DÉFINITION DES ESPACES VERTS ?	CONFLITS D'USAGES (ENTRE HUMAIN.E.S ET NON-HUMAINS)

- 1. Distribution et accessibilité**
 - Fragmentation des infrastructures vertes
 - Publique/prive
- 2. Pollutions (air, nuisances sonores, sols...) - inégalités des impacts/ n'impacte pas tou.te.s**
- 3. Instrumentalisation des espaces verts par le marché**
 - Spéculation immobilière
- 4. Quel public prend part à la définition des espaces verts ?**
 - Capacité de mobilisation/recours
 - Inégalités dans la participation du processus de décision et de définition (« usual suspects »)
- 5. Conflits d'usage (entre humain.e.s. et non-humains)**
- 6. Qualité biologique**

Groupe 3

ACCES SOCIO- CULT. CULT. AUX ESPACES	IMPACT CHANG. CLIM. SUR QUARTIERS PAUVRES
POL. URBA- NISTIQUE SOCIALE, ...	CADRE DE VIE QUAR- TIER
PART. CI- TOYENNE	LOGEMENT (TAILLE, JARDIN, ...)

- 1. Impact changement climatique sur quartiers pauvres**
 - Eau, température...
 - Les quartiers pauvres sont plus exposés aux risques (pics de chaleurs)
- 2. Accès socio-culturel aux espaces**
 - Sécurité
 - Appartenance
- 3. Participation citoyenne**
 - Concertation
- 4. Logement (taille, jardin,...)**
 - Vert/quartier - accès au logement dans un cadre vert ou avoir un jardin (cher)
- 5. Cadre de vie quartier**
- 6. Politique urbanistique, sociale, ...**
 - Perception des politiques
 - Les politiques urbanistiques créent des inégalités notamment dans la manière dont les différents groupes sont perçues par les politiques, à Bruxelles les politiques voient les citoyens comme des classes moyennes blancs.

11. Barriere des langues/internationalisation/ diversités culturelles

Groupe 2

Passé	Politiques des grands parcs (19^e)
	Loi de Taeye 1949 : étalement urbain pavillonnaire
	Complexité décisionnelle + législative
	Crise du logement
	Maintenance vs. soin
2024	COVID-19 (visibilité des conflits d'usage)

Général :

1. **Une brique dans le ventre (+ lois) ; frénésie de la construction**
2. **Croissance démo + attractivité**
3. **Déficit financier régional**
4. **Déficit représentation**
5. **Négligence des enjeux écologiques**
6. Outils et plans d'urbanisme (PRAS)
7. Inégalités % justice
8. Pantouflage politique (manque de responsabilité)
9. Maintenance et soins → anthropocentrés – ex. : un arbre est à abattre si représente un danger pour l'homme, gestion du risque anthropocentrés
10. Complexité admin

Groupe 3

Passé	Industrialisation : Héritage de l'ère industrielle de Bruxelles dans la structure des quartiers
	Ignorance des logiques de la nature
	Incohérence niveaux différents pouvoir 90's
	Perte de la maîtrise foncière 90 - '00
	PRAS/RRU
2024	COVID : exacerbe des inégalités déjà présentes mais a surtout augmenté les prix des biens près d'espace verts.

Général :

- **Capitalisme**
- **Ségrégation socio-économique des populations ; gestion raciale**
- **Vision productiviste de la nature ; par rapport au bien foncier - rentabilisation du bien foncier, la terre n'a pas de valeur, elle en gagne en construisant**
- **Libéralisation du marché immobilier ; perte de la maîtrise du marché en terme du prix**
- **Non-régulation du marché locatif**
- **Manque consultation/représentativité populaire**
- **Changement climatique et manière de la prendre en compte**
- Vision courttermisme politique
- Intérêts et pouvoirs politique du secteur immobilier
- Fragmentation des niveaux de pouvoirs avec la régionalisation - administrativement et politiquement fragmentés

Exercice 3

« Quelles sont les actions phares à mettre en œuvre pour lutter contre ces inégalités tout en assurant la transition vers la neutralité carbone et la résilience climatique en 2050 ? »

... au niveau du quartier

- Less béton
- Prendre en compte et intégrer la diversité des citoyens
- Stop destruction ! changement paradigme/imaginaires
- Citoyen décideur principal
- Une gestion des espaces verts comme des « communs » à l'échelle des quartiers (participation, décision, gestion)
- Déterminer à l'échelle de quartier les besoins en infrastructures vertes avec la participation des habitants/citoyens
- Moratoire sur les constructions sur les sols vivants

... au niveau de la commune

- Stop béton
- Stop destruction → changement paradigme/imaginaires
- Prise de position pro-protection (esp. Nature)
- Suppression des communes vers La Région avec des antennes et échevin – commune cfr Paris
- Le soin comme responsabilité pour les décisions
- Rôle de facilitateur entre région et quartier accompagnant pour actions concrètes
- Fusion administration – commune vers région
- Végétalisation, renaturation
- Assemblées [citoyennes] décisionnelles
- Programmes écoles communal : Nature, sorties, végétalisation, potagers
- Moratoire sur les constructions sur les sols vivants
- Une plus grande transparence des arbitrages et des décisions en matière d'aménagement
- Obligation de créer espaces verts accessible à tous dans projet urbanistiques

... au niveau de la région

- Protection réelle et immédiate des espaces naturels
- Agir pour limiter la spéculation immo
- Cadastre + répartition des infrastructures verts
- Régulation prix logement : loyers encadrés/bloqués
- Limiter nouvelles constructions
- Obligation de créer espaces verts accessible à tous dans projet urbanistiques
- Foncier = bien commun
- Rénovation urbaine inclusive (sans gentrification)
- Augmentation et diversification de l'offre dans zones carencées
- Collecte de données
- Baromètre satisfaction des espaces verts/nature
- Politique coordonnée RBC (urbanistique, sociale, culturelle,)
- Régulation du marché immobilier
- Moratoire sur les constructions sur les sols vifs
- Stop destruction → changement paradigme/imaginaires
- Régionalisation de tous les espaces verts – transferts des communes vers régions

- Stop béton
- Débétonner les espaces publics
- Statut de protection des espaces verts de fait
- Prise en charge isolation bâti pour particulier x région avec remboursement en cas de Vente ou héritage

... au niveau fédéral

- Stop béton
- Stop destruction → changement paradigme/imaginaires
- Changement loi permettant consultation populaire et citoyenne
- Contrôler le prix des logements pour favoriser mixité sociale
- Moratoire sur les constructions sur les sols vivants
- Légiférer sur les droits des non-humaines
- Meilleure répartition des richesses (impôt pour financer meilleure qualité des espaces verts et accessibilité)
- Étendre principe de prévention et précaution aux inégalités socio-environnementales
- Foncier = bien commun (diminution de droit de propriété)
- Nouveaux outils individus - droit de la nature et personnalité juridique

Appendix 4. Outcomes of the Thematic Workshops on Social-Ecological Inequalities in Housing

Exercice 1 : «Quelles sont les principales inégalités sociales-écologiques en matière de logement dans la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale ?»

Groupe 1

7. Qualité des logements

- Production de logements publics dans certains quartiers
- Accès aux services, espaces publics

8. Coût du loyer

9. Accessibilité aux primes à la rénovation, aux informations, etc.

10. Maitrise et connaissance des nouvelles technologies

- Gestion des équipements, régulation technique dans les bâtiments

11. Localisation

12. Impacts des obligations

- Risque de revente, et donc de concentration de la propriété dans les mains de quelques propriétaires, avec impacts sur les locataires
- Impacts sur les locataires et les propriétaires

Groupe 2

7. **Non-recours aux droits et aux mécanismes d'aides**
 - Primes rénovation et énergie : locataires <> propriétaires
 - Cloisonnement des aides
 - Fragmentation des aides
 - Manque d'informations
8. **Participation représentative et effective aux politiques de logement et de la ville, particulièrement des plus précaires**
9. **Conditions économiques de choix et d'accès aux équipements et aménagements moins énergivores et/ou verts**
 - Pour se chauffer, économiser de l'eau
10. **Proximité des espaces verts**
 - Logements sociaux
 - Bâti du centre-ville
 - Densité du bâti
 - Événements climatiques extrêmes
11. **Qualité de l'air**
 - Impact air extérieur versus intérieur ?
12. **Accès à un logement abordable de bonne qualité**
 - Isolation chaud/froid
 - Salubrité
 - Espace adapté à la famille

Groupe 3

1. Accès au logement abordable et de qualité réduit
2. Accessibilité aux alternatives énergétiques et à la capacité d'action
3. NIMBY → Opposition environnement et logement social
4. Inégalité dans la sphère d'influence des politiques publiques
 - Inégalités d'accès ou d'influence dans les politiques publiques de logement → Certains intérêts mieux défendus, avec plus d'influence
5. Certificat PEB injuste socialement et peu adéquat pour réduire réellement les consommations
6. Logements abordables situés dans les quartiers denses, peu verts, soumis à la pollution sonore et atmosphérique + îlots de chaleur

Groupe 4

- **Inégalités financières (revenus + patrimoine)**
 - Différentie propriétaires et locataires
- **Accès aux outils de rénovation (primes, crédit...) en fonction des revenus, du réseau, de l'expertise et des connaissances techniques (pour les propriétaires)**
 - Lien avec effet Mathieu, ceux qui ont le moins de moyen sont exclus
- **Logement social versus pas de logement social - logement bien isolé versus vieux logement (loterie)**
 - Accès au logement social : plus de gens sur liste d'attente
- **Accès à la justice**
 - On n'ose pas déclarer un logement insalubre, un loyer excessif, ou de s'être fait avoir par des entrepreneurs
- **Accès aux systèmes tels que les communautés d'énergie, énergie propre, transition**
 - Utilisés par la classe moyenne, certaines classes ont moins accès.
- **Accès à un environnement de qualité, santé, vert, sécurité et mobilité**

Exercice 2 : « Quels sont les facteurs clés qui ont conduit à l'état actuel de ces inégalités ? »

Groupe 1

Passé	1989 : Création de la RBC → Politiques pro classe aisée (contexte institutionnel belge complexe, région sous-financée, d'où fiscalité favorable aux classes aisées)
	Ghettoïsation → Quartiers denses
	Décentralisation
	Arrivée des institutions européennes à Bruxelles → augmentation des loyers
2024	Manquements politiques foncière et aménagement du territoire

Général :

- **Fiscalité / Taxation**
- **Numérisation des services** → non-recours aux droits, manque d'information pour publics plus précaires, très marquée après COVID
- **Absence d'encadrement des loyers** = « La » cause (Commission paritaire locative = pied dans la porte, mais pas la panacée)
- Normes SEC (EU) → difficile d'investir et de créer du logement social à cause de ces normes
- Trop de pouvoir aux communes par rapport à la région pour la création de logement
- Touristification (Airbnb) → impact sur les loyers et occupation des logements
- Manque de contrôle des logements → DURL n'a pas les moyens de contrôler tous les logements
- Système des primes (rénovation et énergie). Des primes pour gens aisés pour relancer l'économie → met de côté une partie de la population
- Rénovation : Lien stratégique social + écologie + économie.

Groupe 2

Passé	Révolution industrielle / Capitalisme → spéculation
	Désindustrialisation et mouvements de populations bruxelloise → ségrégation (croissant pauvre)
2024	Sous-financement de la Région et des services (administrations et ASBL)
	Lasagne institutionnelle → impacts (fragmentation des aides, on ne sait pas à qui s'adresser)
	Opposition verdure <> production de logements sociaux
	Multiplicité des crises depuis le début du XXIe siècle (Corona, Inondations en Belgique, Guerre en Ukraine, crise de l'énergie) → effets socio-économiques (précarisation) et sur les décideurs politiques (difficultés d'appréhender autre chose que le court terme)

Général:

- Mauvaise qualité des logements sociaux (mauvaise qualité dans le choix des matériaux de construction)
- Manque effectif de logements sociaux (production)
- Choix politiques sur les réserves foncières mal informés ou allant dans le sens d'une marchandisation (PRAS, Tour et Taxis et autres friches, PAD)
- Indexation des loyers des passoires énergétiques
- Manque d'investissement dans la rénovation des logements sociaux
- Contrats de quartier durables : trop peu de budget social
- Rénovation : trop peu sociale et pas assez accompagnée

Groupe 3

Passé	19 ^e siècle : Industrialisation → Croissant pauvre
	Après-guerre → Mauvaise qualité du bâti + techniques pensées sur énergies peu chères !
	Années 50-80 : Bruxellisation
	Crises énergétiques
	Propriété privée > Intérêt collectif
	Clientélisme et court-termisme électoral dans communes et RBC
	Sous-financement structurel de la RBC
2024	Digitalisation → Non-recours aux droits + perte de contacts
	2007 : Libéralisation du marché de l'énergie
	2007 : Politique PEB

Général :

- **Absence de vision globale en RBC**
- Discrimination / stigmatisation. Stigmatisation et dévalorisation des métiers de la construction → malfaçons et déficit de mains d'œuvre chronique
- Limites géographiques de la RBC ! - bloque des politiques : le territoire ne s'étendra pas
- **Fiscalité favorise capital mobilier et immobilier sur fiscalité du travail**

Groupe 4

Passé	1973 : 1ere crise énergétique → Importance de l'enjeu environnement / climat assez récent (et progressif)
	Le public a investi dans le privé au lieu de faire des logements sociaux
2024	Poids des propriétaires du secteurs immobilier dans les décisions → peu de courage politique
	2022 : crise énergétique → Importance du facteur prix (montre qu'un signal prix fait plus changer les comportements que la sensibilisation)
	Coût de la rénovation et de la construction
	Problèmes budgétaires de la RBC

Général:

- **Spécificité du bâti bruxellois, ancien disparate → comment le rénover ?**
- Inexistence de normes de qualité du logement jusqu'il y a peu
- **Histoire de la RBC - Avant régionalisation : peu d'intérêt du fédéral (→ pas de norme de qualité du logement), régionalisation, évolutions démographiques (accompagnées de questions de multiculturalité)**
- **Fonciers limités du fait des limites de la région → conflit entre les différents enjeux, concurrence entre les différents usages**
- NIMBY → accentue les inégalités

Exercice 3 : « Quelles sont les actions phares à mettre en œuvre pour lutter contre ces inégalités tout en assurant la transition vers la neutralité carbone et la résilience climatique en 2050 ? »

Politiques au niveau du quartier

- Les contrats de quartier devraient avoir comme priorité de promouvoir et encourager la rénovation collective
- Développer des antennes de proximité pour pallier la fusion des communes
- Actions d’inclusivité autour des lieux de vie ; création d’espaces d’échanges et de groupes de parole autour des besoins des habitants (en matière de logement + de cadre de vie)
- Info-sessions sur les mesures concrètes à prendre pour 1) Isoler partiellement son logement par rapport aux besoins ; 2) aérer son logement + conseils pour rénovations à impact (Communal ?)

Politiques au niveau de la commune

- Maintenir l'accès à des services publics (versus numérisation)
- Réquisitionner les logements inoccupés pour les mettre à disposition des plus précaires
- Favoriser les rénovations groupées dans certains quartiers (accord des services d'urbanisme)
- Service urbanisme doit faciliter la rénovation énergétique (dérogations, pompes à chaleur)
- Soutien aux initiatives par rapport aux énergies alternatives
- Éducation précoce et continue aux enjeux environnementaux
- Plus de social dans les LQD
- Un quota de 30% de logements sociaux dans les projets « privés »
- PROMOUVOIR, EXPERIMENTER - Une ville produite par et pour les habitants : a) CLT, COOM, habitats groupés, logements sociaux, b) partenariats secteur public / citoyens
- Véritable concertation avec l'ensemble des acteurs (habitants, commerçants, associations...)
- Fusionner les communes et monter certaines compétences à la région

Politiques au niveau de la région

Loyers

- Encadrement/régulation (contraignant) des loyers (5)
- Régulation des loyers et de leurs augmentations actuelles qui sont trop hautes
- Encadrer de manière structurelle les loyers (gel → baisse)
- Encadrement et baisse des loyers + conventionnement en lien avec l'octroi de primes
- Conventionnement des loyers / respect grille des loyers
- Encadrement des loyers (si aide financière à la rénovation (régionale) notamment)
- Encadrer les prix des loyers après une rénovation
- Gel des loyers 5 ans si bailleur obtient primes Révolutions
- Limitation de l'indexation des loyers pour les passoires énergétiques
- Interdire l'indexation des logements à faible PEB (2)

Rénovation énergétique

- Création de « Territoires zéro Logements Passoires énergétiques » dans les quartiers plus défavorisés
- Transformer la logique de primes individuelles en investissements publics collectifs (ex. : isolation des façades de toute une rue → + économique, efficace et démocratique)
- Éviter au maximum les effets Matthieu (et d'aubaine pour le secteur privé de la rénovation) par une politique plus ambitieuse et volontaire de rénovation publique des logements privés par des opérations « groupées » de travaux publics (par rue, quartier)
- Révision du système de primes régionales pour plus d'accessibilité
- Aides régionales pour propriétaires pauvres : prise en charge de 100% du coût de la rénovation. En échange, Propriétaire cède le foncier (système CLT) → Décarbonisation / Démarchandisation
- Faciliter, accompagner, préfinancer l'investissement dans les énergies vertes (panneaux, pompes à chaleur...)

- Plan de rénovation du bâti avec organisation du relogement des personnes qui ne peuvent pas y rester pendant les travaux
- Mise sur pied d'un opérateur public d'énergie et de rénovation
- Améliorer l'accès aux sources d'énergie renouvelable
- Encourager les communautés d'énergie au niveau local → nouvelles réglementations

Consommations réelles

- Inclure consommations réelles dans obligations PEB → favorise la non-consommation choisie
- Tenir compte des consommations réelles comme objectif final dans Révolution

Logements sociaux / publics

- Plus de production de logements sociaux
- Faciliter l'accès aux logements sociaux et en faire davantage
- Plus d'investissement public dans les logements sociaux pour rénovations et productions
- Refinancer massivement la politique de rénovation et de construction de nouveaux logements sociaux pour répondre réellement aux besoins en la matière dans la population Bruxelloise
- Augmenter la masse budgétaire régionale pour la construction de logement sociaux de qualité
- Refinancement des logements publics
- Ne pas construire le métro 3 pour garder des moyens financer pour le logement public et les CLT
- Mettre le budget du métro 3 dans les questions de logement publics, construction, rénovation, entretien...
- Le logement social à revaloriser comme actif financier pour surmonter l'obstacle des normes SEC
- Faciliter et promouvoir le dispositif AIS
- Réfléchir à d'autres outils qui permettent de créer du logement public dans le bâti existant (petite échelle) → contrats de quartier, logements vides, ...
- 25% de logements strictement sociaux dans les prescriptions des plans d'aménagement directeurs
- Pour toutes les nouvelles promotions : Imposer 33% de logement social ou accessible à très long terme
- 100% de logement publics, dont minimum 60% de sociaux sur les terrains publics (pareil pour l'échelle communale)
- Moratoire sur les nouveaux logements privés à but lucratif (uniquement CLT, logements sociaux, housing deal, coop...)

Foncier

- Stop à la cession de foncier/bâti public au privé
- Ne plus jamais vendre un foncier public. Scinder la valeur du sol de la valeur de la brique (CLTB) lorsqu'on développe du logement acquisitif (cf. : City Dev)
- Limiter – encadrer les questions foncières (achat / accès / prix / usages / fonctions...) et arrêter d'opposer logements et espaces verts

Droit au logement

- Reconsidérer le logement comme un droit
- Plus de sécurité vis-à-vis des propriétaires
- Renforcer les possibilités d'expropriation des logements insalubres, vides, tenus par des marchands de sommeil

Gouvernance

- Meilleure entente inter-régionale, BXL – Flandre
- Compétences urbanisme, environnement et logement pour un.e seul.e ministre

Autres

- Captation des plus-values
- Débétonnons massivement (→ biodiversité, îlots de chaleur, ruissellement, etc.)
- Financer suffisamment le secteur associatif pour accompagner et informer

Politiques au niveau fédéral

- Régulation des loyers au niveau fédéral via taxation + limite indexation en fonction du PEB
- Taxation des loyers (réels) (2)
- Fiscalité plus égale entre patrimoine et travail (fédéral mais aussi autres ministres à mobiliser)
- Fiscalité plus avantageuse pour les propriétaires qui mettent leur logement en gestion en AIS
- Fiscalité à revoir pour inclure éléments de justice sociale et environnementale/climatique ; lutter contre la financiarisation du logement
- Lier le précompte immobilier à la qualité (énergétique et autre) du logement
- Revalorisation des ressources humaines (métiers) et matérielles locales pour le secteur de la construction et de la rénovation
- Vraie politique de remise en location des logements inoccupés (+ que des sanctions de type amendes qui n'aboutissent pas toujours à la remise en occupation)
- Augmentation de la dotation / financement de Bruxelles
- Élargissement de la RBC à la zone métropolitaine (Brabant)
- Éliminer tout forme de cloisonnement : les responsables politiques qui œuvrent pour une transition énergétique juste devraient travailler ensemble et inclure les différents niveaux de décisions
- Sortie traité Européen énergie

Transversal

- Re-publicisation (dé-marchandisation) du foncier assortie de projets associant fonctions collectives et espaces verts (biodiversité)
- « Experts du vécu » partout

Appendix 5. Outcomes of the Thematic Workshops on Social-Ecological Inequalities in Mobility

Exercice 1: Les inégalités socio-écologiques

Groupe 1 :

- Accès aux processus participatifs (biais de la représentativité, décrédibilisation d'une partie des usagers)
- Déploiement inégal et qualité inégale des infrastructures (pistes cyclables, trottoirs, transports en commun): spatial, offre
- Moyens dans le choix modal (financiers, compétences / habitude, perception des différents modes) au niveau des individus, des ménages et des groupes
- Pollution de l'air / bruit dans les parties centrales pauvres + accaparement de l'espace public par le tout à la voiture
- Différentiel d'expériences vécues / signification des mobilités (mobilités contraintes mal vécues)
- Inégalités sociales dans la demande de transport avec la complexité du mode de vie (travail de nuit, besoins différents, modes de vie différents..)

Groupe 2 :

- Inégale attention sur les finalités de la mobilité : moins d'attention quand hors du modèle des déplacements domicile-travail (ex : voitures de société), en dehors de la mobilité des classes moyennes, en fonction du travail (ex : espaces centraux avec un certain type d'emploi, les emplois moins qualifiés sont moins accessibles)
- Inégalité d'accès aux décisions politiques et aux informations, question écologique complexe/difficile à saisir qui entraîne une disparité d'accès aux décisions.
- Inégalité d'accès à la mobilité active / au vélo / vélo électrique (vélo : classe sociale, niveau étude, habitation) (vélo électrique : modèle voiture, capacité financière, autres injustices liées à la faible réparabilité)
- Inégalité d'accès au territoire via l'accès au logement (une bonne localisation permet de faire davantage de choses), gentrification (les ménages les plus pauvres ont un bon accès mais sont exclus des quartiers centraux)
- Inégal accès à la mobilité automobile selon les revenus, le genre et donc création de distances pour ceux qui sont hors du système
- Inégale répartition des nuisances associées au trafic routier (pollution air, bruit, accident de la route, occupation Espace Public...) selon le revenu, le mode de déplacement et l'âge (Enfants)

Groupe 3 :

- Inégalités d'accès aux ressources du territoire : lieux d'enseignement, logement, espaces de vie récréatifs, lieux de travail
- Recours inégal à l'action collective : processus participatif (ex : quartiers apaisés), désobéissance civile perçue différemment en fonction des publics qui portent le discours (ex : Comité anti Good Move considéré violent quand le blocage du bois de la Cambre est considéré comme de la désobéissance civile)
- Inégalités d'exposition aux nuisances : qualité de l'air, bruit ; espaces de vie de qualité, perçu comme « sûr »
- Choix de financements / investissements et d'aides publiques répartis inégalement
- Inégalités (impacts différents) face aux mesures contraignantes et de régulation de la voiture en ville (signal prix) qui affectent différemment certains types de métiers (ex : LEZ, électrification). Les politiques ciblent certaines voitures, mais pas les voitures de société. LEZ serait OK si possibilité de report modal et accès aux voitures moins polluantes.

- Inégalités d'accès physique aux modes de transport et de compréhension des différents systèmes de mobilité : accès, compétences, besoins.

Exercice 2. Les facteurs explicatifs : Comment en est-on arrivé là ?

Groupe 1:

- 1920s : Logiques sectorielles = transport pensé comme techniques (biais validisme) & Culture technocratique fonctionnaliste et néo-classique des transports
- 1930s : transformation de l'occupation de l'espace public (stationnement en voirie)
- 1950s : Tout à la voiture (développement routes, RRU, lobbying pétro-industriel)
- Colonisation de l'imaginaire : valorisation de la vitesse et du progrès)
- 1968-1989 : Prise de conscience écologique mais concrétisations faibles
- 1989 : Régionalisation (lasagnes institutionnelle ; Rapports de force entre région qui questionnent l'autonomie de la RBC en matière de mobilité, moins de financement)
- Polarisation du débat
- Prise en compte tardive de l'accessibilité universelle + bashing de la diversité raciale etc...
- Faible espace pour la pensée scientifique dans le débat

- Socialisation différenciée aux risques (genre, classe, race)
- Capitalisme : créé différents régimes de propriété, factorisation de la production sur les questions d'émancipations sociale par rapport à la mobilité, convergence d'intérêts entre public et privé.

Groupe 2:

Groupe 3:

+ /- 1900 : développement d'une industrie automobile

Détricotage transports collectifs

Tout à l'auto : industrialisation et démocratisation de l'accès à la voiture, aménagement du territoire pro-voiture, consommation et distinction

- Augmentation des demandes de mobilité, et étalement urbain (effet boule de neige)
- Résolution de l'équation de l'inégalité au niveau de la mobilité: généralisation de la voiture (voiture longtemps pensé comme une solution aux inégalités → encore en train d'essayer de casser ce paradigme)

- Dégradation de l'état social et des politiques de solidarité : individualisation de la voiture qui contribue au détricotage des solidarités (plus de contact dans les transports en commun / mais la voiture peut être partagée)

- Gouvernance : éclatement des responsabilités et compétences (en mobilité), manque d'intégration des différentes politiques, complexité politique. Horizontale : mobilité vs logement vs cohésion sociale → pas de synergie. Pas calibrée pour penser les enjeux de long terme. Décalage temporel au niveau politique qui se retrouve aussi au niveau des citoyens (plaisir immédiat vs impacts négatifs sur le collectif)

- Socialisation différenciée à la mobilité, pas autorisé en tant que H/F à utiliser l'espace public de la même manière

- Conception technicienne de la politique de mobilité

- Conscientisation politique des enjeux climat vs invisibilisation des impacts écologique

Exercice 3: Les action-phares à mettre en place

Politiques au niveau fédéral

- Politiques de réduction des distances : ville 15 minutes, baisse des déplacement travail-domicile

- Supprimer les voitures de société x4

- Rehausser les revenus de remplacement (RIS, GRAPA, chômage...) pour qu'ils atteignent au minimum le niveau de taux de pauvreté, qu'ils épousent mieux la hausse du coût de la vie

- Refinancement de la Région

- Interdiction du stationnement en voirie

- Stop aux financements publics de la mobilité automobile individuelle

- Renforcer l'accès au TERR en TP (gratuité, cohérence lieux avec TP, augmentation de l'offre)

Politiques au niveau régional

- Renforcer l'accès au TERR en TP (gratuité, cohérence lieux avec TP, augmentation de l'offre)
- Développer l'offre publique de mobilité : TEC, modes partagés publiques – axée sur la pauvreté en mobilité
- Développer le transport public de surface : plus d'accessibilité et moins d'emprise de l'automobile
- Meilleure intégration des services et tickets des opérateurs de mobilité
- Diminuer voire rendre gratuits les transports en commun pour les résidents Bruxellois
- Réforme fiscale qui s'adresse au poids et à la puissance des voitures x2
- Stop aux financements publics de la mobilité automobile individuelle
- Application du principe STOP
- RRU ambitieux pour un meilleur partage de l'espace public
- Stopper la densification des espaces centraux, déjà denses
- Assurer la présence d'équipements publics sur tout le territoire régional
- Urbanisme temporaire comme ouverture des possibles en terme d'occupation de l'espace public
- Politique de logement (sociaux, convention loyers)
- Accès aux logements abordables
- Démocratiser l'accès au logement
- Assurer une meilleure participation (en amont et plus contraignante) des différents groupes qui composent la population bruxelloise (ex : un modèle réellement pris en compte de convention citoyenne)
- Changement institutionnel région / Communes

Politiques au niveau communal

- Accès aux logements abordables

- Application du principe STOP
- Stop aux financements publics de la mobilité automobile individuelle
- Meilleur partage de la voirie au bénéfice d'infrastructure inclusive pour les mobilité actives et véhicules intermédiaires

- Education et sensibilisation aux enjeux d'inclusivité dans la mobilité (enfants et adultes)

Politiques au niveau des quartiers

- Accès à des parkings vélos sécurisés
- Application du principe STOP

Appendix 6. Example of Variable-Sheet: Urban Form of Brussels

Definition

Understanding the Urban Form of BCR helps to grasp the physical form and structure of urban environments that were created in the region. This includes understanding the evolution of urban design, with its population and building density, and the functional use of these urban spaces. This analysis is crucial for planning future green space, mobility, and housing scenarios. It helps identify opportunities for creating green spaces (But also what caused its fragmentation), how the transport network was conceived, what type of modes of transport were promoted, and how transportation infrastructure can be improved and develop high-density, mixed-use housing. Understanding these patterns is essential for initiating a sustainable transition and achieving carbon neutrality in cities like Brussels.

Indicators

- 1) Social-spatial typology map
- 2) Population density per commune (table and map)
- 3) Build Surface per commune (table)
- 4) Office Building density in BCR (map)
- 5) Impermeable surface in BCCR (map)
- 6) PRAS (map)

Retrospective of the variable

1) Urban designs of Brussels

“Histoire de planifier: urbanisme aux 19e et 20e siècles” by Michel De Beule. The book delves into Brussels' planning history from the 19th to early 21st centuries. It contrasts two critical planning approaches: 19th-century urban art and early 20th-century scientific territorial planning, revealing how they have shaped the city. It highlights the discrepancies between idealized district conceptions and their actual realization, showcasing the city's ongoing planning sagas.

- a) **Industrial Revolution:** Brussels was the biggest industrial city in Belgium, and its industrialization significantly shaped its urban dynamics and infrastructures, which still today are key elements explaining the spatial configuration of the region's social problems (Corijn et al., 2013; Ryckewaert et al., 2021). The Senne River is also a configuring element of Brussels' urban development (Ermans et al., 2023). The construction of the Charleroi Canal (in the south of the river), redevelopment of the Wille-Broeck Canal, and the creation of railways during the 19th century (Tours & Taxis is a good emblem of this era) have reinforced Brussel's industrialization, becoming an important industrial and commercial carrefour (Corijn et al., 2013). Multiple factories sprang up around the canal and railways, from breweries to steel industries and lead factories (Corijn et al., 2013). From the 20th century onwards, the industrial basin of the canal expanded and stretched over to the municipalities of Molenbeek Saint-Jean, Anderlecht (Cureghem), and Brussels (with Laken & Neder-over-Heembeek), transforming and urbanizing the center of the region. It is also in those municipalities around the canal that working-class districts were settled. This was also reinforced by the Senne Valey separating Brussels between a gently sloping, marshy alluvial plain to the west and steeper hillsides to the east, which form the edges of a sandy plateau (Ermans et al., 2023). Where the aristocratic and bourgeois elites settled predominantly on the steeper, better-drained slopes and higher ground, and the working class would settle in la “ville basse” (Ermans et al., 2023).

- b) **Bruxellisation and Modernization of Brussels:** This phenomenon has heavily marked the building morphology of Brussels since the second half of the 20th century, whether urbanistically, sociopolitically, or governance-wise. It was set at the beginning of the 1950s; there was political will to transform Brussels into a modern, functional tertiary center of national and international scope, with significant infrastructure projects (urban highways, administrative cities, etc.) (Matthieu). The Bruxellisation corresponded, therefore, to this radical and uncontrolled modernization, which launched the renovation and construction of apartment and office buildings (to follow the tertiarization of the Brussels economy and in the context of the glorious thirty), urban highways (with the rise of car ownership/ “du tout à la voiture), and the demolition of working-class districts and industrial zones (Leloutre, 2022; IEB, 2024). The most illustrating examples are the “Place de Brouckère” towers and the “Quartier Nord” with the Manhattan Project. The Manhattan Project consisted of creating “a huge business district covering more than 50 hectares, with 58 towers, including eight for the World Trade Center project alone. Above all, this project was conceived on a blank page, totally disregarding the 11,000 inhabitants expropriated to make way for the office towers” (IEB, 2024; Comhaire, 2012; Leloutre, 2022). “While the term “bruxellisation” is associated with Brussels, it is more broadly illustrative of a mode of city production specific to Belgium as a whole, based on minimal intervention by public authorities in urban space. Although governance has since improved considerably, with public players such as the regional Master Architect, this approach remains largely valid today. It explains the difficulties in Belgium and Brussels in truly controlling urban development.” (Leloutre, 2022).
- c) **Suburbanization and urban sprawl of Brussels:** After 1945, Brussels experienced significant suburbanization driven by substantial economic growth (“glorious thirty” period and the middle-class boom), middle-class preferences for single-family properties, and the rise of automobile use (Corijn et al., 2013). This suburbanization, characterized by a lack of planning like the rest of Belgium, led to scattered housing developments (Poelmans & Van Rompaey, 2009). Brussels' suburbanization was unique socially and geographically, unlike other European cities, persisting over time and significantly shaping the urban area's layout (Poelmans & Van Rompaey, 2009; Corijn et al., 2013). Accessibility, neighborhood interactions, and road networks primarily influence urban sprawl in Brussels (Poelmans & Van Rompaey, 2009). Areas with better transportation access and proximity to existing urban centers attract more development. Both national and local roads play crucial roles in urban growth, forming commercial and industrial corridors (Poelmans & Van Rompaey, 2009). Furthermore, Brussels and nearby cities like Leuven are major employment hubs, promoting urban expansion. Additionally, young adult households who prefer urban living but desire affordable single-family homes with private gardens are driven to suburbanize due to prohibitive city center prices (Slegers et al., 2012). This leads to two main strategies: relocating to the suburbs or moving further from the city center to avoid high housing costs in inner belts (Slegers et al., 2012).
- d) **Densification and Gentrification (Van Crielingen, 2013):** Since the 1990s, the BCR has launched revitalization policies. The main objective was to make old central neighborhoods more attractive for private investment, particularly in housing, to curb the exodus to the periphery and encourage the return of the middle class to the city. To achieve this, the policies focus on maximizing the impact on private investors through public investments in central neighborhoods. These include incentives for new or renovated housing (renovation grants, tax rebates, and housing subsidies), commercial offerings improvements, and public space improvements (embellishments and surveillance). While social cohesion is also a stated goal, it is secondary to attracting the middle class. The predominant focus on the latter shapes the strategies and measures implemented. (* Additional note: It started when the Brussels Capital region was created. It was also an excellent opportunity to consolidate its fiscal base and

budget and create a sense of democratic legitimacy and identity). The canal zone was the subject of many real-estate projects; good examples of gentrification are Up-site Tower, Tours & Taxis, Gare Maritime, and Kanal Centre Pompidou—the site of Citydev.Brussels has a list of ongoing and finished projects which concern the reconversion of old industrial infrastructure into housing or mixed-use buildings.

Figure 64: The first picture (top right) is the Up-Site tower at Quai des Péniches, right in front of the canal. The second picture (top right) is Vandermaelen housing buildings in Molenbeek Saint-Jean near the metro Comte de Flandre. The third picture (bottom right) is a future project called CityGate Petite île, which will be a mixed-use infrastructure (housing and commercial) stemming from the reconversion of an old pharmaceutical factory in Anderlecht (2025-2030). (Citydev.Brussels)

Figure 65 Social-spatial typology map from the work of Alice Romainville. It is an interesting map depicting a spatial typology (social division) of neighborhoods in BCR, which influences the strategies of private real-estate promoters. As observed, neighborhoods

Bruxelles: typologie spatiale

2) Population density

Figure 66: BCR's population density per commune in 1989 and 2023 (IBSA,2023)

Position	Commune	1989	Commune	2023
1	Saint-Gilles	17,987	Saint-Josse-ten-Noode	22,994
2	Saint-Josse-ten-Noode	17,933	Saint-Gilles	19,519
3	Koekelberg	13,450	Koekelberg	18,997
4	Schaerbeek	13,276	Schaerbeek	16,558
5	Etterbeek	12,599	Molenbeek-Saint-Jean	16,363
6	Ixelles	11,552	Etterbeek	15,607
7	Molenbeek-Saint-Jean	11,414	Ixelles	13,817
8	Ganshoren	8,534	Ganshoren	10,498
9	Forest	7,538	Jette	10,350
10	Jette	7,498	Forest	9,157
11	Woluwe Saint-Lambert	6,615	Evere	8,629
13	Berchem-Sainte-Agathe	6,330	Berchem-Sainte-Agathe	8,615
13	Brussels Capital Region	5,975	Woluwe Saint-Lambert	8,192
14	Evere	5,822	Brussels Capital Region	7,642
15	Anderlecht	5,000	Anderlecht	6,982
16	Woluwe Saint-Pierre	4,312	Bruxelles	5,874
17	Bruxelles	4,171	Woluwe Saint-Pierre	4,753
18	Uccle	3,334	Auderghem	3,940

19	Auderghem	3,258	Uccle	3,766
20	Watermael-Boitsfort	1,928	Watermael-Boitsfort	1,957

Green = The commune's position has not changed since 1989

Yellow = The commune's position has changed since 1989

The population density within the BCR has grown since 1989, with districts located in the first crown and those adjacent to the second crown experiencing a relatively higher increase. However, the geographical distribution of the population/of this density has not significantly changed since 1989, in the sense that the districts with the highest densities have remained consistent over time. In 2022, the highest population densities were mainly found in the center (Pentagone) and the first crown of BCR, gradually decreasing with the distance from the city center. The center of BCR and the first crown encompass the densest areas, notably due to the vital presence of semidetached apartment buildings (IBSA, 2020) * (to verify with the housing stocks and prices to see any correlation and verify if any other factors must be considered).

Notable dense areas of the center and the first crown include (IBSA, 2020):

- In the South: Districts of Bosnie (34,994), Porte de Halle (25,349) and Haut-Saint Gilles (19,239), Marolles (18,747).
- In the West: historical districts of Molenbeek (24,127) and Koekelberg (24,393), Anneessens (23,294)
- In the Northeast: Districts of Saint-Josse Centre (30,894), Chaussée de Haecht (24,737), and Quartier Brabant (23,943).
- In the East: Matonge(18,809) and Flagey-Malibran (20,741)

Figure 67: Maps of RBC's population density per district in 1991 (left) and in 2022 (right) (IBSA, 2022)

However, some central and first crown areas have lower densities due to office concentrations, notably in the European and North quarters. Concerning the second crown, densities were higher in districts alongside the first crown, ranging from 18,000 to 21,000. There is also a difference between the western areas of the second crown, which have relatively higher densities than the East and Southeast. This difference can be partially explained by the prevalence of three- and four-front buildings typical

of open-order housing estates ***(verify housing stocks and prices)** and larger green areas in the East and South-East of the second crown (IBSA, 2020).

Figure 68: Population density per statistical sector (Ermans et al., 2023)

3) Build Surface

Table 1: Evolution of build surface in ha per commune in 2005 and 2023 (IBSA, 2024)

Commune	Build surface in 2005 (ha)	The proportion of build surface in the commune's total area in 2005	Build surface in 2023 (ha)	The proportion of build surface in the commune's total area in 2023	Evolution of build surface in ha between 2005 and 2023
Anderlecht	756,2	42%	845,1	47%	+12%
Auderghem	273,3	30%	290,6	32%	+6%
Berchem-Sainte-Agathe	153,6	52%	172,6	58%	+12%
Bruxelles	1 385,7	42%	1 489,0	45%	+7%
Etterbeek	210,6	66%	212,4	67%	+1%
Evere	222,4	43%	231,0	45%	+4%
Forest	326,0	52%	343,9	55%	+5%
Ganshoren	110,3	45%	118,3	49%	+7%
Ixelles	391,6	61%	410,5	64%	+5%
Jette	260,2	50%	272,4	52%	+5%
Koekelberg	65,6	55%	67,5	57%	+3%
Molenbeek-Saint-Jean	307,9	51%	330,1	55%	+7%
Saint-Gilles	162,6	64%	164,9	65%	+1%
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode	70,3	61%	74,7	64%	+6%
Schaerbeek	441,8	56%	455,2	58%	+3%
Uccle	1 013,4	44%	1 113,3	49%	+10%
Watermael-Boitsfort	261,0	20%	278,0	21%	+7%
Woluwe-Saint-Lambert	386,7	53%	418,0	57%	+8%
Woluwe-Saint-Pierre	476,3	53%	508,2	57%	+7%

Brussels Capital Region	7 275,7	45%	7 795,6	48%	+7%
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Figure 69: Occupation of the Brussels territory (Ermans et al., 2023)

FIGURE 5 :
Occupation du territoire bruxellois

It gives an idea spatial distribution of the built-up density in the BCR.

A) Office building density (IBSA, 2018):

In 2018, the Pentagon and the first crown concentrated most of the offices in the BCR, while the second crown had a smaller share. The eastern half of the Pentagon had office densities over 500,000 m²/km², with Notre-Dame-aux-Neiges having the highest at 1,711,023 m²/km² and Anneessens the lowest at 77,498 m²/km². In the first crown, the European Quarter had the highest density in the region at 2,546,748 m²/km². Châtelain and Matongé had densities between 300,000 and 400,000 m²/km². Most western first crown neighborhoods had moderate densities of 50,000 to 200,000 m²/km², except for the Northern Quarter, which had a high density of 916,102 m²/km² due to the concentration of offices around the North Station.

The second crown of BCR had much lower office densities compared to the first crown. Most neighborhoods in the western second crown had less than 20,000 m² of offices per km². Closer to the first crown, areas like Vieux Laeken East, Vieux Laeken West, Basilique, Karreveld, and Anderlecht-Centre-Wayez had densities between 20,000 and 52,000 m²/km². Further west, neighborhoods such as Berchem Sainte-Agathe Centre, Vogelenzang-Erasme, and Bizet-Roue-Ceria had densities between 20,000 and 47,000 m²/km². In the southern second crown, around Uccle, most office densities were below 20,000 m²/km², except for Globe, Churchill, and Vossegat-Roosendaal, which approached 40,000 m²/km². In the eastern second crown, neighborhoods like Université, Dries, Watermael Centre, Boitsfort Centre, Auderghem Centre, Val d'Or, and Gribaumont had higher densities (50,000 to 150,000

m²/km²) due to major infrastructures and roads such as Boulevard du Souverain, Chaussée de la Hulpe, the E40 and E411 highways, and Avenue de Tervueren. The northeastern second crown, including NATO-Industry, Avenue Léopold III, and Reyers, also showed notable densities.

From 2007 to 2018, the overall office density in the region rose from 77,002 m²/km² in 2007 to 80,394 m²/km² in 2014, then decreased slightly to reach 78,002 m²/km² in 2018. The spatial distribution remained stable between 2007 and 2018.

Figure 70 Office building density (m²/km²) per district in BCR between 2007 (left) and 2018 (right) (IBSA, 2018)

B) Impermeable surface in BCR (IBSA, 2022):

The highest proportions of impermeable surfaces in Brussels are concentrated in the Pentagon and the first crown. Nearly all neighborhoods in the Pentagon have over 95% impermeable surfaces, except for the Royal Quarter at 81% due to Brussels Park. The first crown also shows high impermeability, with most neighborhoods exceeding 85%. Notably, neighborhoods like Duchesse, Cureghem Bara, Porte de Hal, Bosnie, Matonge, Quartier Brabant, Gare du Midi, Historic Molenbeek, Koekelberg, Quartier Européen, Saint-Josse Centre, and Gare de l’Ouest have over 90% impermeability. Chasse, Chaussée de Haecht, and Flagey-Malibran approach 90%. In the first crown, park neighborhoods (Botanique, Cinquantenaire, Parc Leopold, Parc Josaphat) have less than 60% impermeability. Second-crown neighborhoods near the first crown generally have 60% to 85% impermeable surfaces, with Vieux Laeken Ouest, Anderlecht Centre-Wayens, and Woeste exceeding 85%. Outer neighborhoods near the regional border usually have less than 60% impermeable surfaces, with exceptions like NATO Industry and Heysel, attributed to green spaces, agricultural land, and vegetated streets. Comparing impermeability with vegetation and building occupancy rates, neighborhoods in the Pentagon and First Crown, with high impermeable surfaces, have the highest building occupancy and lowest vegetation rates. Second-crown neighborhoods, with lower impermeable surfaces, show lower building occupancy and higher vegetation rates.

Figure 71: Proportion of impermeable surface (%) per district in BCR in 2022 (IBSA, 2022)

Moyenne régionale / Médiane régionale: 53.2

4) Functional use of BCR urban area

- a) The Regional Land Use Plan (PRAS) covers the entire BCR territory. It is a regulatory tool made up of maps (graphic prescriptions) and provisions (literal prescriptions) dividing the territory into zones according to the different activities permitted there. The PRAS is legally binding. The map of the PRAS gives an approximate indication of the different functions/uses of the BCR's urban tissue.

Figure 72: PRAS map from Brugis (Brussels Perspectives, s. d.)

Ingredients of the future

- 1) Michael Ryckewaert, Jan Zaman, and Sarah De Boeck's work, "Variable Arrangements Between Residential and Productive Activities: Conceiving Mixed-Use for Urban Development in Brussels," delivers mixed-used strategies for urban developments based on the examination of three recent live-work mix projects developed by a public real estate agency in Brussels. They investigate how different spatial layouts shape the links between productive, residential, and other land uses and how potential conflicts between residents and economic actors are mediated (Ryckewaert et al., 2021)
- 2) Bruxelles 2040 (2012): The report is not as recent, but it can give an indication of the visions actors had and maybe still have in terms of the major priorities and actions to be implemented by 2020, with an evolving perspective of sustainable regional development in 2040. This includes urban designs, mobility, housing, etc. (Cobbaut et al., 2012)

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